

Towards Fitness-for-purpose assessment in HealthData@EU

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18	BFARM	BUNDESINSTITUT FÜR ARZNEIMITTEL UND MEDIZINPRODUKTE	DE
19	HIQA	HEALTH INFORMATION AND QUALITY AUTHORITY	IE
20	ISS	ISTITUTO SUPERIORE DI SANITA	IT
21	CESSDA ERIC	CESSDA ERIC	NO
21.1	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN - KNAW	NL
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QUANTUM
THE HEALTH DATA QUALITY LABEL

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

DQ	Data quality
DQ&U	Data quality and utility
DQ&U&M	Data quality, utility and maturity
EHDS	European Health Data Space
F4P	Fitness-for-purpose / Fit-for-purpose
HDAB	Health Data Access Body
DH	Data Holder
DU	Data User

Executive summary

We propose the initial design of a Fitness-for-Purpose (F4P) mechanism for HealthData@EU that complements the QUANTUM Data Quality, Utility and Maturity label by capturing Data Users' assessments of how well a dataset serves specific EHDS secondary-use purposes and making results visible via Health Data Access Bodies (HDAB) catalogues. It specifies what to capture—purpose-linked scoring (with an overall average) initially for EHDS Article 53(1) purposes (e.g., scientific research—including AI training/testing, public-health surveillance, policy-making/HTA, statistics, education), aligned with QUANTUM Data Quality dimensions (e.g., completeness, consistency, accuracy), plus one free-text comment and optional elements (e.g., data quality reports, analysis code, DOIs in Zenodo/GitHub); when to report—after data use, within EHDS Article 61(4) timelines, with optional early feedback to Data Holders (DHs); and how to govern—HDAB validation (including moderation) with DH review/response prior to publication, open-source tooling reusable by HDABs, portal-level visualisation (filters by purpose, score thresholds, usage counts; sunburst charts, and temporal trends), and RDF/DQV representation (via `dqv:UserQualityFeedback`) for machine-readable linkage to datasets, the QUANTUM label and permits. The model was developed through 14 expert interviews across 8 institutions, a 20-participant consortium workshop, and an external Project Forum with up to 18 validators (voters). This initial design concentrates on structural and operational aspects and explicitly leaves a detailed F4P scoring methodology out of scope, to be refined through a community-based, data-type-agnostic process in line with QUANTUM's approach. The report concludes with 11 recommendations and focused open items—e.g., on obligatoriness, purpose granularity, and validation resources—to be resolved during prospective implementation and alignment with HealthData@EU.

1. Introduction

The EHDS (European Health Data Space) establishes several provisions for its prospective implementation through various EU funded projects. The objective of the QUANTUM project is to develop a data quality and utility (DQ&U) label in compliance with EHDS Article 78 [\[1\]](#), with a primary focus on the quality labelling of the datasets by Data Holders before the submission of the datasets into the Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs) cataloguing portals. This quality labelling currently stands as a quality, fitness-for-use and maturity specification according to the QUANTUM specifications. However, in the EHDS workflow for secondary use of published datasets (Figure 1), there is also a need to consider the quality of datasets given their multiple intended purposes, information to be prospectively displayed along the quality label at HDABs. However, Article 78 does not address this need, as a meaningful way for users to make application decisions. Such a Fitness-for-Purpose (F4P) mechanism complements the data quality, fitness-for-use and maturity assessments developed in QUANTUM - agnostic to data categories, data holders' maturity and purpose - by providing the user's perspective on the degree to which a dataset is of quality for a specific secondary use. This aligns with the EHDS regulation, highlighting the importance of enabling users to understand whether a dataset can meet the needs of particular purposes such as research, public health, policy-making, or AI development.

This work aims to design this F4P assessment system to incorporate the user's perspective regarding the suitability of datasets for specific secondary use categories, with the goal of providing recommendations for prospective implementation acts complementing the QUANTUM data quality labelling system.

Figure 1. EHDS workflow showing Quality and Utility assessment and Fitness-for-Purpose assessment based on QUANTUM.

Regarding the F4P objectives, the EHDS comprises several articles addressing how users are expected to interact with and use datasets made available via HDAB European data portals, highlighting the importance of user-driven access and secondary use. Article 61 (Box 1) classifies the duties of health data users, in which they shall make public any results or output

of the secondary use, where we suggest the inclusion of the fitness-for-purpose assessment. Further, Article 53 (Box 2) classifies the purposes that can potentially be the target for the datasets whose F4P quality is to be determined. Additionally, article 57 (Box 3), describes the tasks of the HDABs, which include that of making public through electronic means the results communicated by health data users pursuant to Article 61(4). Lastly, the TEHDAS2 project aligns: its recommendations call for post-analysis reporting to HDABs, pave the way for structured F4P, and promote a systematic user-to-holder feedback loop to strengthen transparency and data quality (Box 4).

Box 1. Article 61 from the EHDS

EHDS, Article 61

Duties of health data users

4. Health data users shall make public the results or output of secondary use, including information relevant for the provision of healthcare, within 18 months of the completion of the processing of the electronic health data in the secure processing environment or of having received the response to the health data request referred to in Article 69.

In justified cases related to the permitted purposes of the processing of electronic health data, the period referred to in the first subparagraph may be extended by the health data access body, in particular in cases where the result is published in a scientific journal or other scientific publication.

The results or output of secondary use shall contain only anonymous data.

Health data users shall inform the health data access bodies from which a data permit was obtained about the results or output of secondary use and assist them to make that information public on health data access bodies' websites. Such publication shall be without prejudice to publication rights in scientific journals or other scientific publications

When health data users use electronic health data in accordance with this Chapter, they shall acknowledge the sources of the electronic health data and the fact that the electronic health data have been obtained in the framework of the EHDS.

Box 2. Article 53 from the EHDS

EHDS, Article 53

Purposes for which electronic health data can be processed for secondary use

1. Health data access bodies shall only grant access to electronic health data referred to in Article 51 for secondary use to a health data user where the processing of the data by that health data user is necessary for one of the following purposes:

- a) the public interest in the areas of public or occupational health, such as activities to protect against serious cross-border threats to health, public health surveillance or activities ensuring high levels of quality and safety of healthcare, including patient safety, and of medicinal products or medical devices;
- b) policymaking and regulatory activities to support public sector bodies or Union institutions, bodies, offices or agencies, including regulatory authorities, in the health or care sector to carry out their tasks defined in their mandates;
- c) statistics as defined in Article 3, point (1), of Regulation (EC) No 223/2009, such as national, multi-national and Union-level official statistics, related to health or care sectors;
- d) education or teaching activities in health or care sectors at vocational or higher education level;

- e) scientific research related to health or care sectors that contributes to public health or health technology assessments, or ensures high levels of quality and safety of healthcare, of medicinal products or of medical devices, with the aim of benefiting end-users, such as patients, health professionals and health administrators, including:
- I. development and innovation activities for products or services;
 - II. training, testing and evaluation of algorithms, including in medical devices, in vitro diagnostic medical devices, AI systems and digital health applications;
- f) improvement of the delivery of care, of the optimisation of treatment and of the provision of healthcare, based on the electronic health data of other natural persons.
2. Access to electronic health data for the purposes referred to in paragraph 1, points (a), (b) and (c), shall be reserved for public sector bodies and Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies exercising the tasks conferred on them by Union or national law, including where processing of data for carrying out those tasks is done by a third party on behalf of those public sector bodies or of Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies.

Box 3. Article 57 from the EHDS

EHDS, Article 57

Tasks of health data access bodies

1. Health data access bodies shall carry out the following tasks:
 - (a) deciding on health data access applications pursuant to Article 67 of this Regulation, authorising and issuing data permits pursuant to Article 68 of this Regulation to access electronic health data falling within their remit for secondary use and deciding on health data requests submitted pursuant to Article 69 of this Regulation in accordance with this Chapter and Chapter II of Regulation (EU) 2022/868, including with regard to:
 - (i) providing access to electronic health data to health data users pursuant to a data permit in a secure processing environment in accordance with Article 73;
 - (ii) monitoring and supervising compliance by health data users and health data holders with the requirements laid down in this Regulation;
 - (iii) requesting electronic health data referred to in Article 51 from relevant health data holders pursuant to a data permit issued or a health data request approved;
 - (b) processing electronic health data referred to in Article 51 such as by receiving, combining, preparing and compiling such data when requested from health data holders and the pseudonymisation or anonymisation of those data;
 - (c) taking all measures necessary to preserve the confidentiality of intellectual property rights, for regulatory data protection and to preserve the confidentiality of trade secrets as provided for in Article 52, taking into account the relevant rights of both the health data holder and health data user;
 - (d) cooperating with and supervising health data holders to ensure the consistent and accurate implementation of the provisions on data quality and utility label in Article 78;
 - (e) maintaining a management system to record and process health data access applications, health data requests, decisions on those applications and

- requests and the data permits issued and health data requests handled, providing at least information on the name of the health data applicant, the purpose of access, the date of issuance, the duration of the data permit and a description of the health data access application or the health data request;
- (f) maintaining a public information system to comply with the obligations laid down in Article 58;
 - (g) cooperating at Union and national level to lay down common standards, technical requirements and appropriate measures for accessing electronic health data in a secure processing environment;
 - (h) cooperating at Union and national level and providing advice to the Commission on techniques and best practices for secondary use and the management of electronic health data;
 - (i) facilitating cross-border access to electronic health data for secondary use hosted in other Member States through HealthData@EU referred to in Article 75 and cooperating closely with each other and with the Commission;
 - (j) making public, through electronic means:
 - (i) a national dataset catalogue that includes details about the source and nature of electronic health data, in accordance with Articles 77, 78 and 80, and the conditions for making electronic health data available;
 - (ii) any health data access application and health data request without undue delay after initial reception;
 - (iii) all data permits issued or health data requests approved as well as refusal decisions, including their justification, within 30 working days of the issuance, approval or refusal;
 - (iv) measures related to non-compliance pursuant to Article 63;
 - (v) results communicated by health data users pursuant to Article 61(4);
 - (vi) an information system to comply with the obligations laid down in Article 58;
 - (vii) information, at a minimum on an easily accessible website or web portal, on the connection to HealthData@EU of national contact points for secondary use of a third country, or of a system established at international level by an international organisation, as soon as the third country or the international organisation becomes an authorised participant in HealthData@EU;
 - (k) fulfilling obligations towards natural persons pursuant to Article 58;
 - (l) fulfilling any other tasks related to making possible the secondary use of electronic health data in the context of this Regulation.

Box 4. Related TEHDAS2 documents

Deliverables already published

D6.2 – Guidelines for data users on good application and access practices [\[2\]](#)

This document briefly touches on the obligations of data users to make their analysis outcomes and results publicly available. Section 7.5 mentions that such results should be shared on the Health Data Access Body (HDAB) website after the analysis is completed.

D7.1 – Guidelines on how to use data in a secure processing environment [\[3\]](#)

Chapter 13, titled “What happens after finishing data analysis,” describes the process by which data users must communicate their results to the relevant HDAB, including any significant findings identified during the analysis.

Documents under public consultation (at the date of this document)

M6.1 – Guidelines for data holders on making health data available for reuse

It recognises that data users may need to report back to the data holders—for example, when they detect errors in the data or when they have enriched the dataset in some way. It notes that “there may be interactions related to errors found by data users in the provided health data or related to enriched datasets.”

In the future, this type of user feedback could evolve beyond error reporting to include Fit-for-Purpose evaluations, where users assess how well the dataset met their intended use.

D6.3 – Guidelines for HDABs on procedures and formats [\[4\]](#)

Section 7.10 again refers to the obligation of data users to report feedback after completing their analyses. It also recommends that HDABs should establish procedures for engaging with health data users on sharing results, which could later extend to structured F4P feedback mechanisms.

M5.4 – Short guide for data enrichment for HDABs, data holders, and data users

Will emphasise that a feedback loop from data users after analysis is essential for ensuring transparency, sharing insights about data processing, and improving data quality.

2. Methodology

To design the F4P component, a multi-step methodology is proposed. First, a draft version of the **F4P mechanism** will be prepared by UPV and Sciensano, addressing key design questions such as when and by whom should the F4P be completed within the EHDS workflow, what type of information or scoring system should be used, and how the assessment could be linked to specific permits, access requests and the QUANTUM DQ&U label. The draft will also explore whether an interoperability standard format such as RDF could describe F4P declarations.

Secondly, **bilateral meetings in the form of interviews** will be held with selected Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs), Data Holders and Data Users **within the QUANTUM project, the project forum and its advisory board**, to gather targeted feedback on the initial draft. These consultations will follow a short Delphi-inspired approach to capture expert input, reach a shared understanding, and ensure that the mechanism reflects real-world practices and expectations from institutions responsible for granting access to health data.

Next, a **workshop** will be organised within the QUANTUM consortium to validate the consolidated findings and finalise the design of the F4P mechanism. Finally, an external validation via a QUANTUM Project Forum with invited stakeholders is aimed to validate and further synthesise the final version of the proposal. The result of this process will be a set of

actionable recommendations to be included in this document and potentially be attached to Deliverable 3.2, aiming to establish a pragmatic and standardised way for data users to express how well a dataset meets their intended secondary use—a critical step toward building trust and promoting responsible reuse in the EHDS.

2.1. Workplan

The plan (see Figure 2) for the fitness-for-purpose (F4P) recommendations includes several steps to ensure proper documentation. The first draft of the F4P proposal was completed by September 2025. In October, bilateral meetings with key stakeholders – including HDABs and Data Holders – were held. The validation wrap-up was planned for November, followed by the workshop with selected partners in December, and a Project Forum in February with external stakeholders to finalise and validate the proposal. The gathered input is consolidated into this document between January and March 2026.

Figure 2. Fitness-for-purpose work plan.

2.2. Initial ideas drafting

Initial brainstorming sessions were conducted to define the core concepts of the Fitness-for-Purpose (F4P) mechanism. These sessions focused on identifying when the F4P process should be applied, which users and actors in the EHDS are involved, and how the F4P workflow should be operationalised. The discussions also explored the possibility of introducing a scoring system or quantification method to contextualise the outcome. Furthermore, they addressed key questions around the potential obligation of performing the F4P assessment, the secondary use purposes it should cover, and whether an RDF-based format—similar to the one used in the labelling tool [5]—should be adopted.

The results of this activity are compiled in Section 3 of this document.

2.3. Bilateral meetings

Bilateral meetings were planned with key project stakeholders, particularly those acting as HDABs, Data Holders and, mainly, Data Users within the QUANTUM project, the project forum and its advisory board. A survey was also considered to collect structured feedback on the initial proposal. The insights gained from these activities helped contextualise the design and inform a more refined draft, which were later validated during the workshop phase.

2.3.1. Procedure

Sessions were conducted online and individually with each participant to enable in-depth and non-contaminated discussions focused on the initial F4P proposal. Meetings were expected to last between 45-90 minutes and will be scheduled between October and November 2025.

Participants received in advance documentation with the F4P proposal, the aim of the interviews as well as the interview guide outlining topics and decision points.

At the outset, explicit permission was requested to audio-record the session exclusively for qualitative analysis. Participants may opt out of recording; in such cases, detailed notes were taken. Recordings and notes were stored securely and pseudonymised.

The first part of the session consisted in providing a brief overview covering:

- the F4P proposal's scope and objectives;
- context and prior work informing the proposal;
- alignment with the project's strategic lines, TEHDAS2 and the European Commission's priorities.

Later, the proposal was presented progressively using a semi-structured interview guide using a shared document, at which both the Interviewed and the Interviewer could modify the content. For each component defined in the initial design draft, participants were asked to:

1. Offer open feedback (perceived value, risks, feasibility, dependencies).
2. Suggest alternative features and options (if necessary) or contextual adaptations specific to the participant role (DU, HDAB, DH).
3. Decide which of the options for each design feature are the most relevant and feasible solution, and a justification for their choice.

Participants were also offered to provide written feedback after their bilateral meeting within five business days, using a brief template (or email, if preferred). Submissions were incorporated into the synthesis alongside the interview notes.

Participants could access at any moment to their answers to the interview, for completion or confirmation (member-checking).

2.3.2. Participants

As mentioned, Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs), Data Holders and, mainly, Data Users within the QUANTUM project, the project forum and its advisory board were the key target for these bilateral sessions.

2.4. Workshop

Next, an internal workshop within the QUANTUM consortium was conducted to validate the proposed Fitness-for-Purpose mechanism within the EHDS framework. All previously gathered information from the bilateral meetings and processed by UPV and Sciensano were reviewed and consolidated during this group session, leading to actionable recommendations to guide future implementations.

2.4.1. Procedure

The workshop was held online and open to the full QUANTUM consortium. It lasted 2.5 hours and was facilitated by UPV and Sciensano teams managing flows, timing and tools.

At the outset, consent was requested to record the plenary for minute-taking and accuracy in the decision log. Breakout notes were captured in shared documents; any quotations used in internal reports will be anonymised.

This was the agenda for the workshop:

1. Introduction: Welcoming and Objectives of the session.
2. Synthesis of bilateral findings.
3. Validation rounds by component: Each F4P component was presented briefly. The primary task for participants was to provide reactions in terms of relevance, feasibility or risks. Also, they were asked to express preferences or select an option. Additionally, Next steps: definition of immediate follow-ups.

Participants' feedback was gathered using a live polling tool (Mentimeter), and results were recorded in the decision log.

First, key themes and results derived from the bilateral interviews were presented. Second, for each feature, participants were asked to provide reactions in terms of relevance, feasibility or risks. Also, they were asked to express preferences or select an option and a brief Likert-scale poll (1-5) was run per component to gauge the level of agreement with the current wording of the proposal. There were three possibilities:

- a) Consensus was achieved in general:
 - i) Vote the level of agreement for the feature (Likert).
- b) A mixture of consensus and no consensus was achieved in some subfeatures:
 - i) Vote the level of agreement for the subfeatures with consensus (Likert).
 - ii) Vote the level of agreement between the two options without consensus (Likert).
- c) No consensus was achieved in general:
 - i) Vote the level of agreement between two options (Likert).

2.4.2. Participants

All QUANTUM consortium members and those interviewed in the previous round were invited, ensuring representation from the different project stakeholders. Finally, 23 participants attended the workshop.

2.5. Project forum

As the last step of the F4P proposal design, an external validation was performed with external stakeholders during the 4th QUANTUM Project Forum, which took place on 12 February 2026, from 12:30 to 14:00h. This online workshop was focused on presenting and validating the concept of the QUANTUM dataset F4P assessment model.

During the forum, we presented the outcomes of the development work and participants had the opportunity to actively contribute to shaping the final model through a hands-on validation exercise of those new versioned design features synthesised based on the project workshop outcomes.

Depending on the level of prior agreement identified during the workshop, for all the features participants were invited to either rate their agreement on a Likert scale, choose between alternative options, or both ratings for distinct parts of the design feature (one with prior agreed design and other with prior disagreement, using the three options listed in the section 2.4.1). Qualitative free text comments on relevance, feasibility, and risks were also collected to complement the voting results, together with an open discussion. Special attention was put to those featured where no consensus was found during previous steps of the methodology to gain extra feedback.

In addition, in this exercise we aimed to classify the votes on the roles for each participant: DH, DU and HDAB. When participants declared combined roles (e.g., DH and DU), each role was counted independently. Similarly, when a respondent declared being both HDAB and DH, one unit was attributed to each role. This approach ensured that role-based analyses better reflected functional participation in the F4P governance model rather than strict self-labelling. The resulting distribution shows a strong representation of Data Holders, followed by Data Users, and a smaller but relevant participation of HDAB representatives.

3. Initial design draft for F4P

To support the FP4 conceptualisation, a set of initial assumptions and three sets of guiding design questions have been identified to steer the development process. The initial assumptions aim to represent design features that cover all the F4P system. The three sets of guiding design questions include **what** the F4P evaluation shall include; **when** in the EHDS workflow the F4P is set (here we use when instead of where since the when determines the

where in the EHDS workflow); and **how** the F4P feedback is presented. Each of the questions then comprises a set of possible design features (DFs), which, in some cases, can be complementary. The departing assumption for this design is that (DA1) “**The F4P feedback is reported by the Data User for a dataset whose use was granted by the HDAB and Data Holder**”.

3.1. What?

Defining what the Fitness-for-Purpose (F4P) mechanism should capture is essential for its design and usability within the EHDS. A central consideration is whether the system should include a scoring mechanism, and if so, whether this score should be purpose-based (tailored to specific secondary use cases such as research, public health, or policy making) or a more generic score applicable across contexts. Additionally, the level of granularity is under discussion—whether the F4P should be accessible at the individual data request level (case-level) or as an aggregated assessment of the dataset’s general suitability (i.e., viewed in a broader perspective for the multiple uses, thus maintaining private the results for each particular use).

Beyond scoring, the content and format of the F4P feedback are also being explored. Options include a dimension-based rating provided by the user (e.g., usefulness, completeness, timeliness), categorised risk levels indicating the likelihood of the dataset meeting its intended purpose, and free-text comments to capture qualitative insights. This combination would offer both structured and contextualised information to enrich the understanding of data usability.

DF1.0	F4P purposes and categories
DF1.0.A	The F4P evaluation feedback by Data Users is automatically assigned to the purposes selected in the data access application for which the data access was granted (can be multiple simultaneously). These include the purposes in EHDS Article 53 (Box 2).
DF1.0.B	Data Users can assign different evaluations to the different purposes selected in the data access application for which the data access was granted. These include the purposes in EHDS Article 53 (Box 2).
DF1.0.C	The F4P mechanism should allow more fine-grained categorisation of purposes beyond those in the EHDS Article 53. Once implemented the F4P, a group of experts will define the list. An “others” option might be available in case the fine-grained purpose is not in the list.
DF1.0.D	In addition to the EHDS Article 53 purposes, at the moment of the F4P evaluation, the Data Users can flag the data use (and the evaluation) to the data categories for secondary use as defined in the EHDS Article 51 (Minimum categories of electronic health data for secondary use).
DF1.0.E	In addition to the EHDS Article 53 purposes, at the moment of the F4P evaluation, the Data Users can flag the data use (and the evaluation) to the health domain, using available categories such as in TEHDAS/HealthDCAT-AP, EMA Data Quality Framework; or study type or health condition, using categories such as MeSH. A faceted system might be used to this end.

DF1.1	<p>F4P scoring system, general, regarding purposes.</p> <p>The F4P will implement a purpose-based scoring system. That is, a score for a given purpose will consist of the average of multiple F4P evaluations for that purpose, being the average calculus established as one of the following options. E.g., given a dataset d, and a given purpose p, and an evaluation denoted as i, the score for the given purpose for the dataset would be the average:</p> $\bar{e}_{d,p} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n e_{d,p,i}$
DF1.1.A	<p>The F4P will implement a generic F4P score averaged across the average score for the multiple purposes as described in DF2.1.A. That is, the different purposes may have the same weight, being the generic FP4 score not affected by unbalanced evaluations across purposes:</p> $\bar{e}_d = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{p=1}^m \bar{e}_{d,p} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{p=1}^m \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n e_{d,p,i} \right)$ <p>Purposes without evaluations will not be considered in the generic average. Disgregation on purpose-specific scores will be possible.</p>
DF1.1.B	<p>The F4P will implement a generic F4P score averaged across all the evaluations for the different purposes. Unlike DF2.1.A, those purposes for a given dataset with higher number of evaluations will have more weight in the final score.</p> $\bar{e}_d = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{p=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^{n_p} e_{d,p,i}, \text{ where } N = \sum_{p=1}^m n_p, \text{ and } n_p \text{ is the number of evaluations for a purpose } p.$ <p>Disgregation on purpose-specific scores will be possible.</p>
DF1.1.C	<p>If the F4P implements a generic F4P score as in DF2.1.A and DF2.1.B, the disgregation on purpose-specific scores will not be possible.</p>

DF1.2	<p>Accessibility of F4P evaluations to Data Users</p>
DF1.2.A	<p>Data Users will be able to access through the HDAB catalogues only the aggregated F4P scores for a given dataset, either general, purpose-specific, or both, but not the specific evaluations.</p>
DF1.2.B	<p>Data Users will be able to access through the HDAB catalogues all the aggregated F4P scores for a given dataset, either general, purpose-specific, as well as the specific evaluations.</p>
DF1.2.C	<p>If Data Users are not able to access specific evaluation scores (DF2.2.A), they will however be able to view only the summary free text comments for the evaluations, under the overall scores.</p>

DF1.3	<p>F4P detail for a dataset evaluation</p>
DF1.3.A	<p>The F4P will allow users to provide specific, separate scores for the Data Quality dimensions of the QUANTUM Label.</p>
DF1.3.B	<p>The F4P system will allow users to categorise the risk level for achieving the different purposes (as defined in DF2.0), e.g., in low, moderate, high.</p>
DF1.3.C	<p>The F4P system will allow the uploading of supplementary files to complement the feedback, such as data user generated data quality reports, code scripts for analysis replicability or data preparation/extraction pipelines. This relates to the TEHDAS D5.4 "Short guide for data enrichment for HDABs, data holders, and data users" (Box 4).</p>
DF1.3.D	<p>Additional questions might be included such as for assessing the accuracy of identifying study components (cohort, endpoints, exposures, comparison group,</p>

	timestamps) and the effort required to prepare the dataset for analysis.
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DF1.4	F4P temporal monitoring of scores (validated, as per 3.2 'When')
DF1.4.A	A temporal monitoring for the dataset scores is not needed at the HDAB portals, since dates will be included in the F4P metadata, and generating these outcomes can be done at the different stakeholders.
DF1.4.B	A temporal monitoring plot or aggregation for the dataset scores will be provided at the HDABs and accessible to all the stakeholders (DU, DH, HDAB).
DF1.4.C	A temporal monitoring plot or aggregation for the dataset scores will be accessible only to DH and HDAB.

DF1.5	F4P Free Text Commentaries
DF1.5.A	Free text commentaries are allowed at a F4P evaluation, enabling users to provide contextual or qualitative feedback. Moderation will be needed by HDAB (see DF1.2 regarding validation).
DF1.5.B	Free text commentaries are not allowed at a F4P evaluation.
DF1.5.C	If free text commentaries are allowed, only one commentary is provided for a dataset. (Less complexity)
DF1.5.D	If free text commentaries are allowed, multiple commentaries are allowed at the different sections of the F4P assessment for more granular feedback (e.g., by DQ dimension). (Higher complexity)

DF1.6	F4P and published research outputs
DF1.6.A	If attaching indexed outputs such as digital objects in Zenodo, github or pubmed to a dataset after its use, these should be associated with the selected purpose/s for that use, and thus be accounted as the dataset F4P results.
DF1.6.B	It is not necessary that those indexed objects in DF1.6A should be associated with the purpose, and thus remain as a generic use output.
DF1.6.C	If DF1.6.A, the number of research outputs can be considered an additional metric for F4P.
DF1.6.D	If DF1.6.A, the number of research outputs should not be considered an additional metric for F4P, but remain as F4P metadata.

3.2. When?

Regarding the timing of the F4P mechanism within the EHDS workflow (Figure 1), two key aspects are being considered. First, the F4P evaluation is envisioned to be reported by the data user through the HDAB platform, ensuring a seamless integration with the existing data discovery infrastructure. This feedback should subsequently be directed to the Data Holder, closing the loop between data provision and actual use. Second, from a temporal perspective, the possibility to deliver the F4P assessment could be enabled immediately after the data permit is granted, or provide this feedback only once the data use is completed, and informed to the HDAB.

DF2.1	Moment for F4P reporting in the EHDS workflow
DF2.1.A	The F4P feedback reporting is possible at any time since the data permit was

	granted to the Data User, in conformance with the deadlines specified in the EHDS Article 61.4.
DF2.1.B	The F4P feedback reporting is only possible after the data use is completed, as indicated by the Data User, in conformance with the deadlines specified in the EHDS Article 61.4.
DF2.1.C	The F4P feedback reporting is only possible after the data permit has expired, and in conformance with the deadlines specified in the EHDS Article 61.4.

DF2.2	Time of validation for the F4P feedback by HDAB (see EHDS Article 57, see DF3.6-regarding the validation process)
DF2.2.A	The HDAB can validate each F4P feedback immediately since it is received for a given dataset, within a predefined time (to be defined by the EHDS implementation acts), and the specific feedback is made public upon validation.
DF2.2.B	The HDAB can validate all the received F4P feedbacks in a periodic basis at a fixed period of validation (to be defined by the EHDS implementation acts), within a predefined time (to be defined by the EHDS implementation acts), and all the validated feedbacks are made public after this time.

DF2.3	Moment of Data Holder's access to F4P feedback for their datasets
DF2.3.A	The Data Holder can access the F4P feedback for their datasets at any moment since these have been submitted, independently of the HDAB validation status (which must be indicated).
DF2.3.B	The Data Holder can access the F4P feedback for their datasets only after the HDAB has validated the reports.

3.3. How?

The implementation strategy of the Fitness-for-Purpose (F4P) mechanism within the EHDS must address how it will be operationalised. A key aspect under consideration is its level of obligatoriness. Should providing F4P feedback be mandatory for all data permits granted, or should it be encouraged through a system of incentives to promote participation without imposing formal requirements?

In terms of scope, the F4P mechanism may align strictly with the first-level secondary use purposes defined by the EHDS—such as research, public health, policy making, or innovation—or go a step further by enabling more fine-grained categorisation. For example, in the research domain, a user could specify that the dataset was used for AI model development, or in the innovation domain, it was used for high-risk AI product design. Such granularity could enhance the interpretability of F4P feedback for future users.

Finally, RDF (Resource Description Framework) is being considered to structure the F4P data, ensuring interoperability and integration with other components of the broader EHDS infrastructure. RDF could help link F4P outputs with dataset metadata, labelling scores, and permit information, forming a consistent semantic layer across the ecosystem.

DF3.1	Mean for F4P reporting
DF3.1.A	The F4P feedback is reported by the Data User using a dedicated F4P form in the specific HDAB platform which provided access to the dataset.
DF3.1.B	The F4P feedback is reported by the Data User using a dedicated F4P reporting tool of the EHDS, interoperable with the EHDS central service developments, e.g., through a standardized RDF document.

DF3.2	Obligatoriness
DF3.2.A	Providing F4P feedback must be mandatory for all data uses under permits granted within the EHDS framework.
DF3.2.B	Providing F4P feedback will be optional for all data permits granted within the EHDS framework (EHDS Article 61: “shall”).
DF3.2.C	In either case, providing F4P feedback should be encouraged via incentives, such as prioritised access, recognition mechanisms, or certification schemes.

DF3.3	Use of RDF for F4P metadata representation
DF3.3.A	The global F4P score for a dataset, including either generic score and purpose based scores, can be represented using RDF to ensure semantic interoperability with the EHDS ecosystem.
DF3.3.B	The individual F4P feedback provided by a data user can be represented using RDF to ensure semantic interoperability with the EHDS ecosystem. This would be transparent to the user, and generated in the form or tool as defined in DF3.1.
DF3.3.C	The RDF structures must enable linking F4P outputs with dataset metadata, DQ&U and Maturity scores at the moment of data access, and permit information.
DF3.3.D	The RDF representation should follow existing vocabularies or ontologies used in the EHDS, or extend them if necessary (see DF3.9 and section 3.3).

DF3.5	F4P evaluation process
DF3.5.A	The F4P evaluation process must be completed in one session, no saving capabilities are available.
DF3.5.B	The F4P evaluation process can be saved and resumed at other moment, thus requiring some mechanism and database for storage. There are technical implications with DF.3.1.
DF3.5.C	As in DF3.5.B but with a deadline (e.g., one month, but to be specified) at which all the progress will be lost if the evaluation has not been completed.

DF3.6	F4P validation process
DF3.6.A	No validation by HDABs is required for the individual F4P evaluations. That is, F4P evaluations by DUs are directly published once submitted.
DF3.6.B	HDABs can validate individual F4P evaluations and, in case modifications or changes are needed, these can be requested to the Data Users, to be completed within a period of time to be specified.
DF3.6.C	Specific moderation would be required in case of free text reports or additional files are permitted. This would require more dedicated resources.
DF3.6.D	Data Holders can be part of the F4P feedback validation. Once a HDAB has validated a F4P feedback, this must be further agreed by a DH before being incorporated in the dataset score and being published.
DF3.6.E	Data Holders are not part of the F4P feedback validation. The HDAB validates and the score and feedback is made public.

DF3.7	F4P scoring mode
DF3.7.A	Every F4P evaluation, independently on the scoring granularity or contextualization as defined in DF2.1 and DF2.3, can be entered (and further displayed) as a 5-star rating.
DF3.7.B	Every F4P evaluation, independently on the scoring granularity or contextualization as defined in DF2.1 and DF2.3, can be entered (and further displayed) as a numerical score within a given (likert) scale (e.g., 0-to-10).
DF3.7.C	A combination of DF3.7.A and DF3.7.B depending on the scoring granularity or context, to be agreed.

DF3.8	F4P scoring visualization
DF3.8.A	The F4P scores for a dataset will be visualized following a 5 star approach (according to the design in DF1.1, this could be disaggregated on purposes, or other contextual metadata).
DF3.8.B	The F4P scores for a dataset will be visualized following a sunburst diagram, with different axes (arcs) for the different purposes.
DF3.8.C	The F4P scores for a dataset will be visualized following a sunburst diagram, with different axes (arcs) for the different data quality dimensions.
DF3.8.D	The F4P scores will be primarily visualized using the DF3.8.A star approach, and additional visualizations following DF3.8B and DF3.8C will be provided.
DF3.8.E	Complementary to the aggregated scores visualization, the F4P results for a dataset will list the individual feedback from data users, showing whether they include reported text comments, which could be visualized.
DF3.8.F	Complementary to the aggregated scores visualization, the F4P results for a dataset will list the individual feedback from data users, showing whether they include additional documents, which could be downloadable.

DF3.9	Attachment of the F4P Label to the dataset metadata (at catalogue level)
DF3.9.A	Using DQV property <code>dqv:UserQualityFeedback</code> (subclass of <code>dqv:qualityAnnotation</code> , see section 3.4), where its target (<code>oa:hasTarget</code>) is the dataset evaluated, and with multiple body entries (<code>oa:hasBody</code>) to represent the multidimensional review (e.g. including, text, stars per dimension...).
DF3.9.B	Using a custom extension of DCAT-AP, e.g., <code>q:userFeedback</code> (extending <code>dqv:qualityAnnotation</code>), with a target to the dataset evaluated, and with custom structure for the multidimensional review (e.g. including, text, stars per dimension...).

4. Results of bilateral meetings

During November and December 2025, 8 interviews with eight institutions (from the QUANTUM consortium) took place. Specifically, 14 people were interviewed during those sessions, whose roles were: 3 Data Users, 2 HDAB, 2 HDAB + Data Holders, and 1 Data User + Data Holder. Sex distribution was unbalanced, with more men participating, as shown in Figure 3. Note that the responses are presented based on the number of interviews conducted (N = 8). Additionally, in some cases, the number of responses exceeds 8 because participants

selected more than one option, whereas in other cases it is fewer than 8 because some participants did not indicate a preference.

Figure 3. Sex distribution in the bilateral meetings.

4.1. What - F4P purposes and categories

Across eight respondents, support was strongest for allowing purpose-specific F4P evaluations: 62.5% (5/8) agreed that data users should be able to assign different evaluations to each EHDS Article 53 purpose selected in the access application, while 50% (4/8) supported an automatic one-to-many linkage of the evaluation to the selected purposes. Only limited support emerged for extending beyond Article 53, with 12.5% (1/8) favouring a more fine-grained purpose taxonomy defined by experts (with an “other” option). Additional tagging at the time of evaluation received mixed backing: 12.5% (1/8) for mapping to EHDS Article 51 data categories and 25% (2/8) for health-domain/study-type/condition faceting (e.g., TEHDAS/HealthDCAT-AP, EMA DQ Framework, MeSH/ICD). Comments reflected a clear tension between simplicity and maximum granularity, with suggestions to capture differences between intended and actual use and to allow updates to purposes after permit approval. A key implementation note is to clarify what purpose information is already captured in the data access application to avoid duplication.

ID	Description	Results
DF1.0.A	The F4P evaluation feedback by Data Users is automatically assigned to the purposes selected in the data access application for which the data access was granted (can be multiple simultaneously). These include the purposes in EHDS Article 53 (Box 2).	4 (50%)
DF1.0.B	Data Users can assign different evaluations to the different purposes selected in the data access application for which the data access was granted. These include the purposes in EHDS Article 53 (Box 2).	5 (62.5%)

DF1.0.C	The F4P mechanism should allow more fine-grained categorisation of purposes beyond those in the EHDS Article 53 . Once implemented the F4P, a group of experts will define the list. An “others” option might be available in case the fine-grained purpose is not in the list.	1 (12.5%)
DF1.0.D	In addition to the EHDS Article 53 purposes, at the moment of the F4P evaluation, the Data Users can flag the data use (and the evaluation) to the data categories for secondary use as defined in the EHDS Article 51 (Minimum categories of electronic health data for secondary use).	1 (12.5%)
DF1.0.E	In addition to the EHDS Article 53 purposes, at the moment of the F4P evaluation, the Data Users can flag the data use (and the evaluation) to the health domain , using available categories such as in TEHDAS/HealthDCAT-AP, EMA Data Quality Framework; or study type or health condition , using categories such as MeSH. A faceted system might be used to this end.	2 (25%)

4.2. What - Accessibility of F4P evaluations to Data Users

Among the eight respondents, there was strong support for maximum transparency in HDAB catalogues. A clear majority (87.5%, 7/8) agreed that data users should be able to view all aggregated F4P scores (general and purpose-specific) as well as the underlying individual evaluations for a dataset. Only 12.5% (1/8) supported restricting catalogue visibility to aggregated scores only, without access to specific evaluations. No respondent supported an intermediate option where only summary free-text comments would be shown in lieu of individual scores. Overall, participants favoured making the full set of results available, while noting that transparency should be implemented “with care” (e.g., appropriate safeguards or contextualisation).

ID	Description	Results
DF1.2.A	Data Users will be able to access through the HDAB catalogues only the aggregated F4P scores for a given dataset, either general, purpose-specific, or both, but not the specific evaluations.	1 (12.5%)
DF1.2.B	Data Users will be able to access through the HDAB catalogues all the aggregated F4P scores for a given dataset, either general, purpose-specific, as well as the specific evaluations.	7 (87.5%)
DF1.2.C	If Data Users are not able to access specific evaluation scores (DF2.2.A), they will however be able to view only the summary free text comments for the evaluations , under the overall scores.	0

4.3. What - F4P detail for a dataset evaluation

Across eight respondents, the most supported option was to align F4P feedback with the QUANTUM Label by enabling separate user scores for the label's data quality dimensions (62.5%, 5/8), largely to preserve simplicity and consistency (with a note that the specific metrics for these scores still need to be defined). Interest was more moderate in adding a risk-level categorisation for achieving different purposes (e.g., low/moderate/high), supported by 25% (2/8), with comments noting that perceived risk may depend on the data user's capabilities. Allowing upload of supplementary materials (e.g., user-generated quality reports, scripts, or data preparation pipelines) received 37.5% (3/8) support, valued for transparency and reproducibility but also raising concerns about burden and potential risks for HDABs/data holders. No respondents supported adding further detailed questions on study-component identification or preparation effort, with feedback suggesting such items may reduce comparability across evaluations.

ID	Description	Results
DF1.3.A	The F4P will allow users to provide specific, separate scores for the Data Quality dimensions of the QUANTUM Label.	5 (62.5%)
DF1.3.B	The F4P system will allow users to categorise the risk level for achieving the different purposes (as defined in DF2.0), e.g., in low, moderate, high.	2 (25%)
DF1.3.C	The F4P system will allow the uploading of supplementary files to complement the feedback , such as data user generated data quality reports, code scripts for analysis replicability or data preparation/extraction pipelines. This relates to the TEHDAS D5.4 "Short guide for data enrichment for HDABs, data holders, and data users" (Box 4).	3 (37.5%)
DF1.3.D	Additional questions might be included such as for assessing the accuracy of identifying study components (cohort, endpoints, exposures, comparison group, timestamps) and the effort required to prepare the dataset for analysis.	0

4.4. What - F4P temporal monitoring of scores

For temporal monitoring of F4P scores (n=8), respondents clearly favoured providing trend visualisation/aggregation at HDAB portals. No one supported omitting temporal monitoring entirely, even if dates are present in the metadata. The most supported option was to make a temporal monitoring plot accessible to all stakeholder groups (DU, DH, HDAB) (75%, 6/8). A smaller share supported restricting trend access to data holders and HDABs only (37.5%, 3/8). Participants also stressed that any temporal view should explicitly account for dataset versioning, consistent with the QUANTUM label approach.

ID	Description	Results
DF1.4.A	A temporal monitoring for the dataset scores is not needed at the HDAB portals, since dates will be included in the F4P metadata, and generating these outcomes can be done at the different stakeholders.	0
DF1.4.B	A temporal monitoring plot or aggregation for the dataset scores will be provided at the HDABs and accessible to all the stakeholders (DU, DH, HDAB).	6 (75%)
DF1.4.C	A temporal monitoring plot or aggregation for the dataset scores will be accessible only to DH and HDAB .	3 (37.5%)

4.5. What - F4P Free Text Commentaries

Regarding free-text comments in the F4P evaluation (n=8), most respondents supported allowing qualitative feedback: 62.5% (5/8) favoured enabling free-text commentaries, while explicitly noting the need for HDAB moderation. A minority (12.5%, 1/8) preferred not to allow free text, citing concerns about added bureaucracy and limited added value. Among those supporting free text, views differed on structure: 50% (4/8) supported a single comment per dataset to keep complexity low while still allowing context, whereas 25% (2/8) preferred multiple section-level comments (e.g., per data-quality dimension) to increase granularity, albeit with higher complexity. Comments also highlighted governance considerations, including whether data holders should be able to respond to user comments.

ID	Description	Results
DF1.5.A	Free text commentaries are allowed at a F4P evaluation, enabling users to provide contextual or qualitative feedback. Moderation will be needed by HDAB (see DF1.2 regarding validation).	5 (62.5%)
DF1.5.B	Free text commentaries are not allowed at a F4P evaluation.	1 (12.5%)
DF1.5.C	If free text commentaries are allowed, only one commentary is provided for a dataset . (Less complexity)	4 (50%)
DF1.5.D	If free text commentaries are allowed, multiple commentaries are allowed at the different sections of the F4P assessment for more granular feedback (e.g., by DQ dimension). (Higher complexity)	2 (25%)

4.6. What - F4P and published research outputs

For linking indexed research outputs (e.g., Zenodo, GitHub, PubMed) to datasets after use

(n=8), most respondents supported purpose-specific association: 62.5% (5/8) agreed that such outputs should be linked to the purpose(s) selected for that use and considered part of the dataset's F4P results. Only 12.5% (1/8) preferred keeping outputs as generic, non-purpose-specific metadata. The same share (62.5%, 5/8) supported using the number of outputs as an additional F4P metric, while 12.5% (1/8) argued it should remain metadata rather than a metric. However, respondents flagged interpretability concerns, noting that more publications do not necessarily imply better fitness for a given purpose, and emphasised that users should be able to attach results even when findings are negative.

ID	Description	Results
DF1.6.A	If attaching indexed outputs such as digital objects in Zenodo, github or pubmed to a dataset after its use, these should be associated with the selected purpose/s for that use, and thus be accounted as the dataset F4P results .	5 (62.5%)
DF1.6.B	It is not necessary that those indexed objects in DF1.6A should be associated with the purpose, and thus remain as a generic use output .	1 (12.5%)
DF1.6.C	If DF1.6.A, the number of research outputs can be considered an additional metric for F4P .	5 (62.5%)
DF1.6.D	If DF1.6.A, the number of research outputs should not be considered an additional metric for F4P, but remain as F4P metadata.	1 (12.5%)

4.7. When - Moment for F4P reporting in the EHDS workflow

On the timing of F4P feedback submission (n=8), respondents strongly favoured collecting feedback after the data use is completed: 87.5% (7/8) supported allowing reporting only once the data user indicates completion, in line with the EHDS Article 61.4 deadlines. A smaller group (25%, 2/8) supported enabling feedback at any time after permit grant, noting it could help data holders identify and correct issues earlier. Very limited support (12.5%, 1/8) was observed for restricting reporting until permit expiry, with concerns that waiting too long could reduce accuracy as users may forget details. Some respondents suggested a hybrid approach—allowing early, provisional feedback that can later be confirmed—while also acknowledging potential risks if premature assessments are recorded.

ID	Description	Results
DF2.1.A	The F4P feedback reporting is possible at any time since the data permit was granted to the Data User, in conformance with the deadlines specified in the EHDS Article 61.4.	2 (25%)

DF2.1.B	The F4P feedback reporting is only possible after the data use is completed , as indicated by the Data User, in conformance with the deadlines specified in the EHDS Article 61.4.	7 (87.5%)
DF2.1.C	The F4P feedback reporting is only possible after the data permit has expired , and in conformance with the deadlines specified in the EHDS Article 61.4.	1 (12.5%)

4.8. When - Time of validation for the F4P feedback by HDAB

Regarding validation of F4P feedback by HDABs (n=8), most respondents preferred continuous validation upon receipt: 75% (6/8) supported validating each feedback within a predefined timeframe (to be set in EHDS implementation acts) and making the specific feedback public once validated. A smaller share (25%, 2/8) favoured periodic batch validation at fixed intervals, with publication after the validation window, noting this may be more feasible operationally. Comments highlighted the need to consider HDAB capacity and resources, and several respondents stressed that data holders should be involved in the validation process. Some also suggested allowing flexibility across HDABs in how validation is operationalised, while keeping the process transparent and time-bound.

ID	Description	Results
DF2.2.A	The HDAB can validate each F4P feedback immediately since it is received for a given dataset, within a predefined time (to be defined by the EHDS implementation acts), and the specific feedback is made public upon validation .	6 (75%)
DF2.2.B	The HDAB can validate all the received F4P feedbacks in a periodic basis at a fixed period of validation (to be defined by the EHDS implementation acts), within a predefined time (to be defined by the EHDS implementation acts), and all the validated feedbacks are made public after this time .	2 (25%)

4.9. When - Moment of Data Holder’s access to F4P feedback for their datasets

Views were split on when data holders (DHs) should be able to access F4P feedback for their datasets (n=8). Half of respondents (50%, 4/8) supported granting DHs access immediately after submission, regardless of HDAB validation status, provided the validation state is clearly indicated. The other half (50%, 4/8) preferred restricting DH access until after HDAB validation. A potential compromise raised in the notes was to allow DHs to view feedback pre-validation (before it becomes public) while prominently displaying a validation flag, enabling early review without conflating unvalidated and validated content.

ID	Description	Results
DF2.3.A	The Data Holder can access the F4P feedback for their datasets at any moment since these have been submitted , independently of the HDAB validation status (which must be indicated).	4 (50%)
DF2.3.B	The Data Holder can access the F4P feedback for their datasets only after the HDAB has validated the reports .	4 (50%)

4.10. How - Mean for F4P reporting

On where F4P feedback should be reported (n=8), opinions were mixed. Half of respondents (50%, 4/8) favoured reporting via a dedicated F4P form within the same HDAB platform that granted dataset access, arguing this aligns with the access workflow and portal-based interaction. A substantial minority (37.5%, 3/8) preferred an EHDS-level reporting tool interoperable with central services (e.g., via a standardised RDF document), citing scalability, extensibility, and potential to reduce operational burden on individual HDABs. Comments suggested there may be no one-size-fits-all solution and emphasised the need for at least a common core model that could be extended by HDABs over time. Respondents also noted that the preferred reporting route may depend on how the QUANTUM label is operationalised (national/HDAB catalogue vs. central services) and that this topic may warrant alignment with parallel discussions (e.g., TEHDAS).

ID	Description	Results
DF3.1.A	The F4P feedback is reported by the Data User using a dedicated F4P form in the specific HDAB platform which provided access to the dataset.	4 (50%)
DF3.1.B	The F4P feedback is reported by the Data User using a dedicated F4P reporting tool of the EHDS, interoperable with the EHDS central service developments, e.g., through a standardized RDF document .	3 (37.5%)

4.11. How - Obligatoriness

Responses were mixed on whether providing F4P feedback should be mandatory under EHDS permits (n=8). Half of respondents (50%, 4/8) supported making feedback mandatory for all data uses, with some suggesting it should be an explicit condition accepted before permit grant and even linking future access to prior feedback. A substantial minority (37.5%, 3/8) preferred keeping feedback optional, pointing to the EHDS Article 61 wording (“shall”) and questioning the feasibility of strict obligatoriness. Regardless of the preferred approach, incentivisation was repeatedly raised: 25% (2/8) explicitly supported encouraging feedback through incentives. However, comments cautioned that certain incentives—particularly prioritised

access—could create unfair discrimination and conflict with EHDS principles, indicating that any incentive scheme would need careful design (e.g., recognition or certification mechanisms rather than preferential access).

ID	Description	Results
DF3.1.A	Providing F4P feedback must be mandatory for all data uses under permits granted within the EHDS framework.	4 (50%)
DF3.1.B	Providing F4P feedback will be optional for all data permits granted within the EHDS framework (EHDS Article 61: “shall”).	3 (37.5%)
DF3.2.C	In either case, providing F4P feedback should be encouraged via incentives , such as prioritised access, recognition mechanisms, or certification schemes.	2 (25%)

4.12. How - F4P evaluation process

On whether F4P evaluations should be completed in one sitting or allow saving progress (n=8), respondents largely supported save-and-resume functionality. Only 12.5% (1/8) preferred requiring completion in a single session with no saving. A minority (37.5%, 3/8) supported saving and resuming without additional constraints, while the most supported option (50%, 4/8) was to allow saving with a deadline (e.g., one month) after which incomplete progress would be discarded. Comments stressed the importance of aligning any save/resume deadlines with EHDS timelines, and one suggestion was to provide a mechanism for users to request post-validation amendments to their assessment via the HDAB.

ID	Description	Results
DF3.5.A	The F4P evaluation process must be completed in one session, no saving capabilities are available.	1 (12.5%)
DF3.5.B	The F4P evaluation process can be saved and resumed at other moment , thus requiring some mechanism and database for storage . There are technical implications with DF.3.1.	3 (37.5%)
DF3.5.C	As in DF3.5.B but with a deadline (e.g., one month, but to be specified) at which all the progress will be lost if the evaluation has not been completed.	4 (50%)

4.13. How - F4P validation process

On validation and moderation of individual F4P evaluations (n=8), there was no support for immediate publication without validation (0%), indicating a clear preference for a controlled workflow. Half of respondents (50%, 4/8) supported HDAB validation with the possibility to

request clarifications or revisions from data users within a defined timeframe. The strongest support was for involving data holders (DHs) in the process: 62.5% (5/8) agreed that, after HDAB validation, DHs should be given a role before feedback is incorporated into scores and published, whereas only 12.5% (1/8) preferred DHs to be excluded entirely. A minority (12.5%, 1/8) explicitly highlighted the need for dedicated moderation when free-text comments or supplementary files are allowed. Qualitative notes emphasised that DH involvement should not become a veto power; instead, DHs should have an opportunity to review and respond to feedback (e.g., to address misunderstandings) within clear deadlines. At the same time, participants warned of potential conflicts of interest if DHs can dilute negative evaluations, reinforcing the need for HDAB oversight and transparent controls.

ID	Description	Results
DF3.6.A	No validation by HDABs is required for the individual F4P evaluations. That is, F4P evaluations by DUs are directly published once submitted.	0
DF3.6.B	HDABs can validate individual F4P evaluations and, in case modifications or changes are needed, these can be requested to the Data Users , to be completed within a period of time to be specified.	4 (50%)
DF3.6.C	Specific moderation would be required in case of free text reports or additional files are permitted. This would require more dedicated resources.	1 (12.5%)
DF3.6.D	Data Holders can be part of the F4P feedback validation. Once a HDAB has validated a F4P feedback, this must be further agreed by a DH before being incorporated in the dataset score and being published.	5 (62.5%)
DF3.6.E	Data Holders are not part of the F4P feedback validation. The HDAB validates and the score and feedback is made public.	1 (12.5%)

4.14. How - F4P scoring mode

Preferences for how individual F4P evaluations should be entered and displayed (n=8) favoured a numeric Likert-type scale. Most respondents (62.5%, 5/8) preferred using a numerical score (e.g., 0–10), while 25% (2/8) supported a 5-star rating. An additional 25% (2/8) suggested a hybrid approach (stars and numbers) depending on the scoring granularity or context, reflecting that the choice was not straightforward for some participants. Several comments pointed to aligning the scoring format with the QUANTUM label approach for consistency, and one light-hearted suggestion proposed using “hearts” instead of stars.

ID	Description	Results
DF3.7.A	Every F4P evaluation, independently on the scoring granularity or contextualization as defined in DF2.1 and DF2.3, can be entered (and further displayed) as a 5-star rating .	2 (25%)

DF3.7.B	Every F4P evaluation, independently on the scoring granularity or contextualization as defined in DF2.1 and DF2.3, can be entered (and further displayed) as a numerical score within a given (likert) scale (e.g., 0-to-10).	5 (62.5%)
DF3.7.C	A combination of DF3.7.A and DF3.7.B depending on the scoring granularity or context, to be agreed.	2 (25%)

4.15. How - F4P scoring visualization

Views on how to visualise aggregated F4P scores were heterogeneous (n=8), with no single dominant format. The most supported primary option was a sunburst diagram by purpose (37.5%, 3/8), while 25% (2/8) preferred a 5-star display. Support for a sunburst by data-quality dimensions was limited (12.5%, 1/8), and a further 12.5% (1/8) favoured using stars as the main view complemented by sunburst visualisations. Beyond the aggregate view, respondents expressed a clear preference for access to supporting detail: 62.5% (5/8) supported listing individual feedback entries and indicating whether additional documents are attached and downloadable, whereas 25% (2/8) supported highlighting the presence of free-text comments. Overall, comments suggested sunburst “at minimum” for purpose-level insight, while also emphasising alignment with QUANTUM label presentation and the value of transparent drill-down to underlying evidence.

ID	Description	Results
DF3.8.A	The F4P scores for a dataset will be visualized following a 5 star approach (according to the design in DF1.1, this could be disaggregated on purposes, or other contextual metadata).	2 (25%)
DF3.8.B	The F4P scores for a dataset will be visualized following a sunburst diagram , with different axes (arcs) for the different purposes .	3 (37.5%)
DF3.8.C	The F4P scores for a dataset will be visualized following a sunburst diagram, with different axes (arcs) for the different data quality dimensions .	1 (12.5%)
DF3.8.D	The F4P scores will be primarily visualized using the DF3.8.A star approach , and additional visualizations following DF3.8B and DF3.8C will be provided.	1 (12.5%)
DF3.8.E	Complementary to the aggregated scores visualization , the F4P results for a dataset will list the individual feedback from data users , showing whether they include reported text comments , which could be visualized.	2 (25%)
DF3.8.F	Complementary to the aggregated scores visualization , the F4P results for a dataset will list the individual feedback from data users , showing whether they include additional documents , which could be downloadable.	5 (62.5%)

4.16. How - Use of RDF for F4P metadata representation

Support was relatively strong for representing F4P information in RDF to ensure semantic interoperability with the EHDS ecosystem (n=8). A majority (62.5%, 5/8) endorsed using RDF to represent the global F4P score(s) for a dataset (generic and/or purpose-based), and 50% (4/8) also supported RDF representation of individual user feedback, generated transparently by the reporting form/tool. The most widely supported requirement was that the RDF structures should enable linking F4P outputs to dataset metadata, the DQ&U and maturity scores at the time of access, and permit information (75%, 6/8), highlighting the importance of end-to-end traceability. Fewer respondents (25%, 2/8) explicitly emphasised aligning with or extending existing EHDS vocabularies/ontologies, though notes indicated these options are not mutually exclusive. A recurring comment stressed the value of packaging the F4P representation “in one file” for ease of exchange and integration.

ID	Description	Results
DF3.1.A	The global F4P score for a dataset , including either generic score and purpose based scores, can be represented using RDF to ensure semantic interoperability with the EHDS ecosystem.	5 (62.5%)
DF3.1.B	The individual F4P feedback provided by a data user can be represented using RDF to ensure semantic interoperability with the EHDS ecosystem. This would be transparent to the user, and generated in the form or tool as defined in DF3.1.	4 (50%)
DF3.2.C	The RDF structures must enable linking F4P outputs with dataset metadata, DQ&U and Maturity scores at the moment of data access, and permit information.	6 (75%)
DF3.3.D	The RDF representation should follow existing vocabularies or ontologies used in the EHDS, or extend them if necessary (see DF3.9 and section 3.3).	2 (25%)

4.17. How - Attachment of the F4P Label to the dataset metadata

For the RDF modelling approach to capture user F4P feedback (n=8), respondents clearly preferred reusing existing W3C vocabulary concepts. Most (62.5%, 5/8) supported using DQV—specifically the dqv:UserQualityFeedback pattern, with the dataset as the target and multiple bodies to represent a multi-dimensional review (e.g., text plus per-dimension ratings). Only 12.5% (1/8) favoured a custom DCAT-AP extension with a bespoke internal structure. Notes indicate the preference for option A was driven by simplicity and interoperability through reuse of established concepts, while acknowledging that an initial DQV-based approach could later be extended toward a DCAT-AP custom profile if needed.

ID	Description	Result
DF3.9.A	Using DQV property dqv:UserQualityFeedback (subclass of dqv:qualityAnnotation, see section 3.4), where its target (oa:hasTarget) is the dataset evaluated, and with multiple body entries (oa:hasBody) to represent the multidimensional review (e.g. including, text, stars per dimension...).	5 (62.5%)
DF3.9.B	Using a custom extension of DCAT-AP , e.g., q:userFeedback (extending dqv:qualityAnnotation), with a target to the dataset evaluated, and with custom structure for the multidimensional review (e.g. including, text, stars per dimension...).	1 (12.5%)

5. Results of the F4P workshop

The Fitness-for-Purpose (F4P) workshop was held on 21 January 2026 as a key milestone in validating the F4P proposal, with a total of 20 participants. The workshop aimed to present the consolidated results of the bilateral stakeholder meetings and to validate the proposed design features through a structured consensus-based approach.

Participants represented different roles within the EHDS ecosystem, including Data Holders, Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs), and Data Users. The session began with a presentation of the main findings from the bilateral phase, which addressed core design questions such as the granularity of purposes, the use of scoring mechanisms, the timing of feedback within the EHDS workflow, governance responsibilities, and integration within EHDS platforms.

A total of ten synthesised design features were presented for validation. Next, the ten synthesised design features and the resultant responses are described.

5.1. What - F4P purposes and categories

This synthesised design feature included the following points:

- The F4P evaluation is assigned to all the purposes selected in the data access application.
 - Either case, users can provide distinct evaluations in case of multiple purposes.
- One of the following possibilities is to be agreed:
 - The purposes are only those in the EHDS Article 53.
 - More fine-grained purposes could be assigned, in a way to be further discussed (faceted list, keywords, potentially using vocabularies).
- Remaining questions:
 - Optionally, the health domain may come from the dataset metadata.

Two elements were subject to voting. First, participants were asked to indicate their overall

level of agreement with the proposed F4P purposes and categories design feature. Second, they were asked to express their position regarding the preferred configuration for purpose granularity – whether purposes should remain strictly limited to Article 53 or whether additional granularity should be allowed.

A total of 18 out of 20 participants voted on the overall design feature, resulting in a moderate level of agreement (mean: 3.9/5). When considering the alternative configurations (15 voters), restricting purposes strictly to those defined in EHDS Article 53 received stronger support (mean: 5.1/7), while allowing more fine-grained purposes (e.g., through faceted lists, keywords or controlled vocabularies) obtained moderate agreement (mean: 4.5/7).

Figure 4. Level of agreement with the overall proposed F4P purposes and categories design feature.

Figure 5. Level of agreement with the two options for the purposes and categories: those on the Article 53 or more fine grained.

The qualitative feedback (11 comments) revealed a careful balance to be addressed. Several participants emphasised that greater granularity would enable more meaningful, purpose-specific evaluations, particularly in complex research contexts, and could support dataset improvement. Others highlighted that limiting purposes to Article 53 would enhance harmonisation and comparability across datasets. Concerns were also raised regarding increased complexity and administrative burden if granularity becomes excessive. Overall, the results suggest that Article 53 purposes should remain the structural baseline of the F4P mechanism, while additional granularity could be considered in a controlled and possibly optional manner to preserve both usability and comparability.

5.2. What - F4P general scoring system

This synthesised design feature included the following points:

- One of the following possibilities is to be agreed:
 - Purpose specific scores + an average score are available
 - Only purpose-specific score is available (no average score)
- The number of completed uses will be a separate metric
- A temporal monitoring plot for all the scores and metrics will be available
- Remaining questions:
 - In case of having average score, it will be based on all the individual scores, not as the average of the scores for each purpose
 - Possibility to show both mean and median score
 - Possibility to show a range/deviation from the averaged scores
 - How to handle as an additional metric the number of published research objects (e.g., articles) and relationship with quality for purpose

Two elements were subject to voting. First, participants were asked to choose between the two alternative scoring configurations: whether the system should include both purpose-specific scores and an additional average score, or only purpose-specific scores without an overall average. Second, they were asked to indicate their overall level of agreement with the general scoring feature as proposed.

A total of 16 out of 20 participants voted on the alternative scoring configurations. The option combining purpose-specific scores with an additional average score received strong agreement (mean: 5.6/7), whereas the option providing only purpose-specific scores (without an overall average) received low agreement (mean: 3.1/7). This indicates a clear preference for maintaining both detailed and aggregated views.

Figure 6. Level of agreement with the two options for the scoring system.

The general formulation of the scoring feature was evaluated by 15 participants, who reported a mean agreement of 4.7/5, reflecting strong overall support.

Figure 7. Level of agreement with the overall general scoring system.

The qualitative feedback (8 participants, 7 comments) emphasised the importance of balancing simplicity and informativeness. Several participants considered the average score useful for high-level decision-making and quick screening, while purpose-specific scores were seen as necessary for more detailed assessments. However, concerns were raised about excessive complexity and the potential for bias, particularly when scores influence users without sufficient contextual explanation. Some participants noted that visual examples would help stakeholders better understand how the scoring system would operate in practice.

Overall, the workshop results support a dual scoring model combining purpose-specific scores with an aggregated average score, provided that the system remains interpretable and avoids unnecessary complexity.

5.3. What - F4P user evaluation contents

This synthesised design feature included the following points:

- Specific scores for the Data Quality dimensions of the QUANTUM Label
- One free text commentary will be allowed (of sufficient length to provide detail)
- Supplemental material could be uploaded (e.g., user generated DQ report, code scripts, analysis reports, preprints, articles...)
 - This could be indexed digital objects (with a DOI, e.g., Zenodo entry, article...)
- Remaining questions:
 - Metrics for the DQ dimensions yet to be defined. Likert was preferred over stars.
 - Significance of additional contents to be further discussed: risk levels, difficulty to define study components (endpoints, comparison group...), effort required to

- prepare dataset.
- Potential burden for HDABs and DHs: hosting needs and moderation requirements.
- Participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement with the proposed structure for F4P user evaluation contents.

A total of 15 out of 20 participants voted on this feature, resulting in a strong level of agreement (mean: 4.5/5), indicating broad support for the proposed structure.

Figure 8. Level of agreement with the user evaluation contents.

The qualitative feedback was limited (4 participants, 2 substantive comments). One participant suggested that an overall score should complement the user evaluation contents in order to improve interpretability. No strong opposition to the structure was expressed. However, open questions remain regarding the definition of dimension-level metrics, the effort required to prepare supplementary material, and the potential hosting and moderation burden for Data Holders and HDABs.

Overall, the results indicate general support for a structured user evaluation model combining dimension-specific scoring and qualitative commentary. At the same time, further clarification is required concerning operational details and implementation burden.

5.4. What - Accessibility of F4P evaluations to Data Users

This synthesised design feature included the following points:

- Data Users will be able to access (through the HDAB catalogues):

- All the general and/or purpose-specific aggregated F4P scores for a given dataset
- All the specific evaluations (those evaluations of other users)
- Remaining questions:
 - Anonymization: only the data user institution is shown for a given F4P feedback, never individual details

Participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement with the proposed accessibility model for F4P evaluations.

A total of 14 out of 20 participants voted on this feature, resulting in a strong level of agreement (mean: 4.7/5), indicating broad support for making F4P evaluations visible within the EHDS ecosystem.

Figure 9. Level of agreement with the accessibility of F4P evaluations to Data Users.

The qualitative feedback (6 participants, 6 comments) focused primarily on governance and privacy aspects. Several participants stressed that only institutional information should be displayed, rather than individual-level identifiers, particularly considering GDPR constraints and the possibility that individuals may leave their institutions. Some suggested that anonymity or optional disclosure mechanisms should be considered. Questions were also raised regarding contact mechanisms for follow-up feedback and whether linking the assessment directly to the data permit could reduce the need for additional contextual information.

Overall, the results suggest broad agreement on making F4P evaluations accessible to Data Users, provided that appropriate safeguards are in place to address anonymity, data protection, and governance considerations.

5.5. When - Moment for F4P reporting in the EHDS workflow

This synthesised design feature included the following points:

- The F4P feedback reporting is only possible after the data use is completed, as indicated by the Data User, in conformance with the deadlines specified in the EHDS Article 61.4 (see below)
 - Feedback can be saved and retaken within the deadlines.
- Early feedback could be shared through the HDAB portals with the DHs, but this will not be officially considered as the F4P evaluation.
- Remaining questions:
 - Early feedback: comment-based discussions at the dataset level at the HDABs?

Participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement with the proposed moment for F4P reporting within the EHDS workflow.

A total of 14 out of 20 participants voted on this feature, resulting in a strong level of agreement (mean: 4.6/5).

Figure 10. Level of agreement with the moment for F4P reporting in the EHDS workflow.

The proposal foresees that official F4P feedback should be provided only after the data use is completed, in line with the deadlines specified in EHDS Article 61.4. Feedback could be saved and completed within the reporting deadlines. In addition, early feedback could be shared through HDAB portals, though it would not constitute the formal F4P evaluation.

The qualitative feedback (5 participants, 4 substantive comments) reflected general

agreement that a proper fitness-for-purpose assessment can be performed only after actual data use. However, participants highlighted several operational considerations. These included differences between timelines for permit granting and for data use completion, the need to clarify information flows (e.g., who informs whom and when data use ends), and whether early discussions should take place directly with the Data Holder rather than through the HDAB. Some participants also emphasised that early assessments may be helpful, but should not replace the final evaluation based on real usage experience.

Overall, the results support positioning formal F4P reporting after data use, while recognising the potential value of informal or preliminary exchanges earlier in the workflow.

5.6. When & How - Validation of the F4P feedback

This synthesised design feature included the following points:

- HDABs can validate each feedback immediately since received, within a predefined time (to be defined), and the feedback is made public upon validation.
 - Validation includes moderation of free text and supplemental material.
- Data Holders must be part of the validation: once a HDAB has validated a feedback, this must be further agreed by a DH before being incorporated in the dataset score and being published.
 - Data holders can reply free text comments.
- Remaining questions:
 - Potential biases and conflicts of interest (eg deletion, moderation) by DHs on negative evaluations. Control by HDABs.
 - Validation and moderation need of resources.

Participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement with the proposed validation model for F4P feedback.

A total of 14 out of 20 participants voted on this feature, resulting in a strong level of agreement (mean: 4.6/5).

Figure 11. Level of agreement with the validation of the F4P feedback.

The proposal foresees that HDABs validate each F4P feedback within a predefined timeframe, including the moderation of free-text comments and supplementary material, before making it public. Data Holders would also be involved in the validation process, and their agreement would be required before incorporating the feedback into the dataset score and publishing it. Data Holders would additionally be able to provide response comments.

The qualitative feedback (5 participants, 5 comments) emphasised the importance of involving Data Holders in the validation process, while ensuring that safeguards are in place to prevent inappropriate moderation or deletion of negative evaluations. Participants stressed the need for precise cooperation mechanisms between HDABs and Data Holders, as well as transparency regarding the visibility of Data Holder responses. Concerns were also raised about the additional resource burden on HDABs and the time required to conduct validation effectively.

Overall, the results support a shared validation model involving both HDABs and Data Holders, provided that clear governance rules, transparency safeguards, and adequate resources are ensured.

5.7. How - Mean for F4P reporting

This synthesised design feature included the following points:

- One of the following possibilities is to be agreed:
 - Feedback is provided through a form at each HDABs (respecting central-services interoperability standards)
 - Feedback is provided through a dedicated, open-source tool, interoperable with

the EHDS and HDABs (HDABs can reuse and extend that tool freely)

- Remaining questions:
 - To be discussed in TEHDAS?

Participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement with the proposed implementation model for F4P reporting.

A total of 15 out of 20 participants voted on this feature.

Providing feedback through a form at each HDABs received limited agreement (mean: 3.2/7), whereas providing feedback through a dedicated, open-source tool interoperable with the EHDS and HDABs received strong agreement (mean: 5.5/7). This indicates a clear preference for a shared, reusable tool over decentralised alternatives.

Figure 12. Level of agreement with the mean for F4P reporting, on how feedback is provided.

The qualitative feedback (5 participants, 4 substantive comments) highlighted practical considerations. Some participants questioned how this discussion aligns with TEHDAS2 work packages, while others stressed the importance of ensuring proper communication channels between Data Users and HDABs throughout the access and feedback process. Concerns were also raised about the need for ongoing maintenance, user support (e.g., helpdesk), training, and sustainable funding for any dedicated tool.

Overall, the workshop results strongly support the development of a dedicated, interoperable open-source tool for F4P reporting, while underlining the importance of governance clarity and long-term sustainability.

5.8. How - Obligatoriness

This synthesised design feature included the following points:

- One of the following possibilities is to be agreed:
 - F4P feedback is mandatory
 - F4P feedback is optional
- Remaining questions:
 - Incentives vs. discrimination.
 - Data Users award/micro-credential mechanisms seem a fair incentive.

Participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement regarding the obligatoriness of F4P feedback.

A total of 16 out of 20 participants voted on this feature.

The option of making F4P feedback mandatory received relatively high agreement (mean: 4.8/7), while making it optional received lower support (mean: 3.5/7). Although neither option achieved a strong consensus, the results indicate a clearer inclination towards some form of mandatory reporting.

Figure 13. Level of agreement with the obligatoriness for F4P feedback.

The qualitative feedback (9 participants, 12 comments) revealed a nuanced position. Several participants questioned how mandatory feedback would be enforced and whether it should be formally linked to the data access permit. Some suggested that at least a brief feedback should be mandatory, provided it remains proportionate and does not create excessive administrative burden. Others warned against punitive or discriminatory mechanisms based on whether feedback is provided.

At the same time, incentives and recognition mechanisms were widely discussed. Proposals included highlighting contributors, introducing awards or micro-credentials, or implementing reward-based systems if feedback remains optional. However, some participants questioned the long-term effectiveness of such mechanisms in changing behaviour.

Overall, the results suggest moderate support for making F4P feedback mandatory, but with strong emphasis on proportionality, feasibility, and the avoidance of discriminatory or overly burdensome approaches. Incentive-based models may complement or soften mandatory requirements.

5.9. How - F4P graphical user interfaces (3 stages in HealthData@EU portals: search, list, detail)

This synthesised design feature included the following points:

- Searching datasets:
 - Filter by purposes, F4P score thresholds, and number of times used
- Listing datasets from search results (multiple datasets listed):
 - Showed purposes tags and their score, number of times dataset used.
- Entering a dataset detail:
 - Sunburst diagram (or similar), with different axes (arcs) for the different purposes (or those searched).
 - Entering purposes: sunburst diagram, with different axes (arcs) for the different data quality dimensions (purpose-specific).
 - List of all individual feedback, sortable by date or results, at which all the detail is accessible (scores, text comments, supplemental material).
- Remaining questions:
 - Minimum Viable Product to be tested and iterated over.

Participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement with the proposed graphical user interface structure for F4P across the three stages of the HealthData@EU portals (search, list, detail).

A total of 14 out of 20 participants voted on this feature, with a mean level of agreement of 4.4/5, indicating strong overall support.

Figure 14. Level of agreement with the F4P graphical user interfaces.

The proposal foresees filtering datasets by purposes, F4P score thresholds and number of times used at the search level; displaying purpose tags, scores and usage frequency in listing views; and presenting detailed visualisations at the dataset level, including sunburst diagrams for purposes and data quality dimensions, as well as sortable lists of individual feedback entries with access to scores, text comments and supplementary material.

The qualitative feedback (4 participants, 2 substantive comments) raised usability considerations. One comment suggested that sunburst diagrams might be excessive for datasets with only one or two purposes, proposing simpler visual indicators (e.g., stars or Likert-style scores) at the purpose level and reserving more detailed visualisations for dimension-level information. Another concern referred to potential bias towards older or more frequently used datasets, highlighting the importance of clearly displaying dataset dates to avoid misleading interpretations.

Overall, the results indicate strong support for integrating F4P visualisations into the HealthData@EU portal structure, while emphasising proportional visual complexity, usability, and safeguards against unintended bias.

5.10. How - Use of RDF as underlying interoperability and computer readability component

This synthesised design feature included the following points:

- An individual RDF file will contain all the F4P data for a given dataset
- The RDF file is linked with the dataset and QUANTUM DQ&U&M label, through dataset UIDs

- The root property is the `dqv:UserQualityFeedback` (subclass of `dqv:qualityAnnotation`), its target (`oa:hasTarget`) is the dataset evaluated, and multiple body entries (`oa:hasBody`) represent the multidimensional review (e.g. including, text, stars per dimension...)
- Remaining questions:
 - Could derive into Health DCAT-AP extension.

Participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement with the use of RDF as the underlying interoperability and computer-readability component of the F4P mechanism.

A total of 13 out of 20 participants voted on this feature, resulting in a very strong level of agreement (mean: 4.8/5).

Figure 15. Level of agreement with using RDF as underlying interoperability and computer readability component.

The proposal foresees that an individual RDF file would contain all F4P data for a given dataset, linked through dataset UIDs to both the dataset and the QUANTUM DQ&U&M label. The structure would rely on the `dqv:UserQualityFeedback` class (as a subclass of `dqv:qualityAnnotation`), with the evaluated dataset as target and multiple body entries representing multidimensional reviews (including scores and textual comments).

The qualitative feedback was limited (3 participants, 2 substantive comments) but generally positive. One comment explicitly supported the proposal, while another highlighted that a more precise specification of the `UserQualityFeedback` property may be required to ensure consistency and proper implementation. The potential alignment with a Health DCAT-AP extension was implicitly seen as a logical next step.

Overall, the results demonstrate strong endorsement of an RDF-based implementation, with minor technical clarifications to be addressed at the specification level.

6. Results of the Project Forum

The 4th QUANTUM Project Forum was held March 12 2026. It consisted in an Online Workshop on Fitness-for-Purpose for Data Quality, and brought together external and internal to QUANTUM participants from diverse roles within the EHDS ecosystem.

During registration, participants could identify themselves as Data Holders (DH), Data Users (DU), Health Data Access Bodies (HDAB), or select “other”, and multiple simultaneous roles were allowed. After applying predefined counting rules to address multi-role declarations and to exclude unclear or non-classifiable categories, the distribution of participants included 11 Data Holders, eight Data Users and three Health Data Access Bodies. Two responses classified under “Other” were excluded from subsequent quantitative analyses, as their placement within the EHDS operational roles was not clearly defined.

Next, the synthesised F4P design features were presented to the Project Forum participants for discussion and validation. Building on the results of the previous workshop, particular attention was given to those elements where lower levels of agreement had been identified. Participants were invited to rate their agreement on Likert scales, choose between alternative configurations, and provide qualitative feedback. The following sections present the results of the forum, structured according to the different F4P design features discussed.

6.1. What - F4P Purposes and categories

18 participants voted on whether the F4P evaluation should be assigned to all purposes selected in the data access application. The overall level of agreement was high (mean: 5.5/7), indicating strong support for embedding Fitness-for-Purpose assessment directly within the declared access purposes.

Figure 16. Level of agreement of the F4P purposes and categories design feature.

When disaggregated by role, Data Users showed the highest level of agreement (6.14/7),

followed by Data Holders (5.00/7) and Health Data Access Bodies (4.67/7). This suggests that Data Users, in particular, perceive clear value in explicitly linking F4P evaluation to the purposes declared in the access request.

Two alternative configurations for defining purposes were then examined. Restricting purposes strictly to those defined in EHDS Article 53 received moderate support (mean: 3.94/7; 14 respondents). Data Users were comparatively more supportive of this restriction (4.67/7), while Data Holders (3.40/7) and HDAB representatives (3.00/7) expressed lower levels of agreement. This distribution indicates that limiting the framework to Article 53 does not generate strong cross-role consensus.

Figure 17. Level of agreement of the F4P purposes and categories design feature: purposes on the article 53 and fine-grained purposes.

By contrast, introducing more fine-grained purposes—through mechanisms such as faceted lists, keywords, or controlled vocabularies—received stronger overall support (mean: 4.82/7; 17 respondents). Notably, HDAB representatives expressed firm agreement (6.33/7), followed by Data Holders (5.00/7), whereas Data Users were more reserved (3.50/7). This divergence suggests that institutional actors may view additional granularity as beneficial for governance, traceability and analytical precision. At the same time, Data Users may be more sensitive to the risk of increased procedural complexity.

The qualitative feedback aligns with this interpretation. Several participants emphasised that more detailed purpose categories would better capture the nuances of research contexts, particularly for large or heterogeneous datasets such as registries. At the same time, there was repeated concern about the risk of fragmentation, inconsistent terminology and increased administrative burden. The importance of a harmonised vocabulary and a manageable structure was consistently stressed. A recurring proposal was to maintain Article 53 as a structural baseline while allowing controlled or optional subcategories to accommodate more specific use cases.

Overall, the Project Forum results confirm strong support for purpose-linked F4P evaluation and indicate a moderate but clear preference for introducing additional granularity beyond Article 53. However, the role-based differences underline the need for a carefully balanced design that enhances analytical value without compromising comparability or usability across stakeholder groups.

6.2. What - F4P general scoring system

A total of 17 participants voted on the proposed F4P general scoring system. The overall level of agreement was 5.00/7, indicating solid but not unanimous support for introducing a scoring framework combining an average F4P score and purpose-specific scores.

When disaggregated by role, differences become visible. Data Users expressed the strongest support (6.0/7), followed by Data Holders (5.0/7), while Health Data Access Bodies showed more moderate agreement (3.0/7). This suggests that Data Users, in particular, see value in a structured scoring system, whereas HDAB representatives may have greater reservations, possibly linked to governance or interpretability concerns.

Figure 18. Level of agreement of the F4P general scoring system design feature.

The qualitative feedback provides important nuance. Several Data Holders and HDAB representatives questioned the use of an average score across all purposes, arguing that such aggregation may obscure whether a dataset is fit for a specific use case. Concerns were raised

about potential bias, misinterpretation, and the risk that an overall score could influence users without sufficient contextual information. Some comments explicitly suggested that purpose-specific scores are more informative and less misleading than a single aggregated metric.

Conversely, Data Users highlighted that an average score could serve as a practical entry point, enabling rapid screening when selecting datasets. From this perspective, an aggregated score may support high-level comparison, provided that more detailed purpose-specific information remains available.

A recurring theme across roles was the importance of balancing simplicity and interpretability. While scoring was generally considered valuable, several participants stressed the need to avoid over-simplification, especially if scores influence decision-making. Some comments even questioned whether scoring should be used at all, emphasising the importance of qualitative F4P feedback instead.

Overall, the Project Forum results indicate moderate to strong support for a structured scoring system combining purpose-specific and aggregated elements. However, role-based differences and qualitative feedback underline the need for careful design to prevent bias, preserve contextual interpretation, and ensure that purpose-specific information remains central to the assessment.

6.3. What - F4P user evaluation contents

A total of 13 participants voted on the proposed structure of the F4P user evaluation contents. The overall level of agreement was 5.62/7, indicating strong support for the proposed model combining dimension-specific scoring, structured free-text commentary, and the possibility of uploading supplementary material.

When analysed by role, Data Holders expressed the highest level of agreement (5.86/7), followed by Health Data Access Bodies (5.33/7) and Data Users (5.00/7). Although support is consistently high across roles, the slightly lower score from Data Users may reflect practical considerations regarding usability or effort.

Figure 19. Level of agreement of the F4P user evaluation contents design feature.

Qualitative feedback adds important context. One Data Holder highlighted that, in previous discussions, both Data Holders and Data Users had experienced difficulties interpreting and scoring Data Quality dimensions. This suggests that dimension-specific scoring may require more precise guidance, shared definitions or additional explanatory material to ensure consistency and reduce ambiguity.

From the Data User perspective, user-generated reports and metrics were seen as potentially valuable contributions, particularly if integrated into the dialogue between Data Users and HDABs during the data application process. This points to a more dynamic and interactive understanding of F4P feedback, beyond static scoring.

HDAB representatives emphasised that user reports could support governance functions, notably by helping verify the validity of the QUANTUM label and flagging datasets that may require revision. This reflects a view of F4P feedback not only as user information but also as a quality-monitoring mechanism.

However, some caution was expressed. One HDAB participant argued that allowing only a single free-text commentary would help avoid excessive noise and questioned the necessity of uploading supporting material. This reflects concerns about the moderation burden, interpretability, and potential information overload.

Overall, the results provide clear support for a structured evaluation model that combines quantitative and qualitative elements. At the same time, the discussion highlights three implementation challenges: ensuring interpretability of DQ dimensions, managing moderation and hosting burdens, and balancing richness of feedback with usability and signal-to-noise considerations.

6.4. What - Accessibility of F4P evaluations to Data Users

A total of 13 participants voted on the accessibility of F4P evaluations to Data Users. The overall level of agreement was 5.85/7, indicating strong support for making F4P evaluations accessible through HDAB catalogues.

When disaggregated by role, agreement was consistently high. Data Users showed the strongest support (6.50/7), followed closely by Data Holders (6.14/7) and Health Data Access Bodies (5.67/7). This alignment across roles suggests a broad consensus that transparency of F4P feedback within the EHDS ecosystem is both desirable and valuable.

Figure 20. Level of agreement of the Accessibility of F4P evaluations to Data Users design feature.

The qualitative feedback focused on governance, differentiation and capacity considerations. One Data Holder raised the question of whether F4P assessments should be contextualised by the type or professional profile of the Data User providing the feedback. For example, researchers might be particularly interested in feedback from other researchers. This suggests potential added value in signalling the respondent's background or category, while still preserving institutional-level anonymity.

At the same time, concerns were expressed regarding the moderation capacity. One Data Holder questioned whether HDABs would realistically have sufficient time and expertise to evaluate and moderate visible feedback. This links accessibility directly to resource implications and governance design.

From the Data User perspective, F4P feedback was seen not only as user information, but as part of the broader governance history of a dataset. Feedback could help demonstrate the dataset's utility and demand, and signal quality expectations or areas for improvement. In this view, making evaluations accessible strengthens accountability and transparency within the data access lifecycle.

Overall, the results show clear and cross-role support for making F4P evaluations visible to Data Users. However, implementation must carefully balance transparency with anonymity safeguards, moderation capacity, and potential mechanisms to contextualise feedback by user profile without compromising data protection principles.

6.5. When - Moment for F4P reporting in the EHDS workflow

A total of 12 participants voted on the proposed timing of F4P reporting within the EHDS workflow. The overall level of agreement was 5.08/7, indicating moderate to good support for limiting official F4P reporting to the moment after data use, in line with Article 61(4) of the EHDS.

When analysed by role, Data Users showed the highest level of agreement (5.50/7), followed by Health Data Access Bodies (5.00/7) and Data Holders (4.57/7). While support exists across roles, the slightly lower score among Data Holders suggests greater hesitation regarding the proposed timing constraints or potential edge cases.

Figure 21. Level of agreement of the Moment for F4P reporting in the EHDS workflow design feature.

The qualitative feedback highlights important boundary conditions. One Data Holder raised the question of how to handle cases in which an application is withdrawn, for example, due to insufficient cases to conduct the intended research. This raises the issue of whether F4P feedback should still be required or possible when the data use does not formally reach completion.

Another Data Holder emphasised that if a dataset proves not to be fit for a given purpose during early discussions, it could be valuable to make this visible—even if no formal data request is submitted. This suggests potential value in capturing structured signals about “non-use” or adverse fit-for-purpose outcomes, beyond completed secondary use.

From the Data User perspective, a clear distinction was drawn between issues related to data

quality and fitness for purpose, and issues related to the data access application process. According to this view, F4P feedback should concern the usability or the inability to use the dataset itself, rather than procedural or administrative challenges during the access request phase.

Overall, the results support anchoring official F4P reporting to the completion (or documented impossibility) of data use, in line with the EHDS legal framework. However, the discussion reveals unresolved questions regarding withdrawn applications, early fit-for-purpose signals, and the boundary between governance/process issues and substantive data usability. These aspects may require further clarification in the operational design of the F4P mechanism.

6.6. When & how - Validation of the F4P feedback

A total of 13 participants voted on the proposed validation model for F4P feedback. The overall level of agreement was 5.00/7, indicating moderate support for a validation process led by HDABs, with Data Holders involved prior to publication.

When disaggregated by role, Health Data Access Bodies expressed the strongest support (5.67/7), followed by Data Holders (5.29/7), while Data Users showed more moderate agreement (4.50/7). This suggests that institutional actors more directly involved in governance and oversight are comparatively more supportive of a structured validation layer. In contrast, Data Users may perceive potential risks of over-moderation or procedural complexity.

Figure 22. Level of agreement of the Validation of the F4P feedback design feature.

The qualitative feedback reveals several governance tensions. One Data Holder questioned whether moderation would extend to validating the Data Users' DQ scores themselves, raising the issue of how far validation should go: procedural moderation (e.g., inappropriate content) versus substantive assessment of the scores assigned.

Another participant expressed uncertainty about why HDABs should be the primary validation

authority rather than Data Holders, suggesting that validation should, at a minimum, be a joint effort. This reflects an underlying debate about institutional roles and responsibilities within the EHDS governance architecture.

At the same time, concerns about bias were explicitly acknowledged. One HDAB representative argued that Data Holders must have the opportunity to respond to feedback, but that their interventions should themselves be subject to HDAB validation to avoid conflicts of interest. In this view, HDAB oversight would apply to both user comments and holder responses, creating a dual-layer moderation system.

The question of how disagreements between Data Users and Data Holders should be resolved was also raised, with one participant suggesting that HDABs serve as the final arbiter in such disputes. This positions HDABs not merely as moderators, but potentially as adjudicating entities within the F4P mechanism.

Finally, the role of trusted data holders and intermediary entities was noted, suggesting that the validation model may need to accommodate diverse governance configurations across Member States.

Overall, the results indicate cautious support for a validation model in which HDABs play a central role, while Data Holders are formally involved prior to publication. However, the discussion highlights unresolved issues regarding the scope of validation, distribution of responsibilities, conflict-of-interest safeguards, dispute-resolution mechanisms, and resource capacity. These aspects will be critical in operationalising a balanced and credible F4P validation framework.

6.7. How - Mean for F4P reporting

A total of 9 participants voted on the proposed implementation model for F4P reporting. The overall level of agreement was 5.67/7, indicating strong support for providing F4P feedback through a dedicated, open-source tool interoperable with EHDS and reusable by HDABs.

When disaggregated by role, support was particularly high among Health Data Access Bodies (6.33/7) and Data Users (6.00/7), while Data Holders also showed solid agreement (5.40/7). This cross-role alignment suggests broad consensus on the need for a technically harmonised and interoperable solution at the European level.

Figure 23. Level of agreement of the Mean for F4P reporting design feature.

The qualitative feedback focused primarily on integration, governance and sustainability. Several participants argued that the functionality should be incorporated into an existing platform rather than developed as a separate, standalone tool. In particular, multiple comments pointed to the HealthData@EU portal as the natural location for hosting and maintaining the F4P reporting functionality. This reflects a preference for central integration over fragmentation.

Questions were also raised regarding the level at which feedback should be provided: national catalogues, European-level portals, or both. This indicates that architectural design decisions will need to reconcile subsidiarity with harmonisation.

From an HDAB perspective, strong support was expressed for making a reusable tool available to Member States. However, concerns were clearly voiced regarding long-term maintenance, governance and funding. One suggestion was to explore whether maintenance costs could be covered through data access-related fees. Sustainability, therefore, emerges as a key condition for implementation.

Finally, one participant warned that allowing extensions of the tool at Member State level could lead to divergent user interfaces, potentially undermining harmonisation. This highlights the tension between flexibility for national adaptation and the need for a coherent user experience across the EHDS ecosystem.

Overall, the results indicate clear support for a centralised, interoperable and reusable F4P reporting tool, ideally integrated within the EHDS digital infrastructure. At the same time, long-term maintenance, funding mechanisms and the balance between harmonisation and national flexibility remain critical open design questions.

6.8. How - Obligatoriness

A total of 15 participants voted on whether F4P feedback should be mandatory. The overall

mean score was 3.60/7, indicating a tendency against making F4P feedback mandatory, though without a fully consolidated position.

When disaggregated by role, differences become more pronounced. Data Holders showed the highest relative support for obligatoriness (4.12/7), though still close to neutrality. Data Users were more sceptical (3.60/7), and Health Data Access Bodies expressed the lowest level of agreement (2.00/7), indicating clear opposition among HDAB representatives to a mandatory model.

Figure 24. Level of agreement of the Obligatoriness design feature.

The qualitative feedback strongly reinforces this pattern. Across roles, concerns were raised that mandatory reporting could:

- Create an additional bureaucratic burden.
- Discourage data use within the EHDS framework.
- This leads to low-quality or perfunctory feedback submitted merely to fulfil a formal requirement.
- Incentivise users to bypass the EHDS and contact Data Holders directly to avoid additional obligations.

From the Data User perspective, several comments stressed that forced feedback tends to be of lower quality and that voluntary contributions are more meaningful. It was also noted that Data Users already have legal obligations to report on outputs and use of data under the EHDS framework, and that F4P reporting should therefore remain optional and distinct from existing compliance duties.

HDAB representatives expressed particular concern that mandatory F4P reporting could undermine the EHDS system's attractiveness by increasing administrative friction. One comment explicitly questioned the feasibility of enforcement, given that users already pay for data access. While incentives were mentioned as a potential mechanism, participants also warned that incentive-based models (e.g., prioritised access) could risk discrimination or unfair differentiation.

Interestingly, even those who recognised the potential value of F4P feedback for future users tended to favour an optional model, at least in the initial implementation phase, until a better balance between utility, fairness and enforceability is identified.

Overall, the results indicate limited support for a fully mandatory F4P model at this stage. The discussion suggests a stronger preference for an optional approach, potentially complemented by soft incentives or partial obligations (e.g., a minimal mandatory component), provided that discrimination and excessive burden are avoided.

6.9. How - F4P graphical user interfaces (3 stages in HealthData@EU portals: search, list, detail)

A total of 11 participants voted on the proposed graphical user interface model for F4P within the HealthData@EU portals. The overall level of agreement was 5.45/7, indicating solid support for integrating F4P visualisation across the three proposed stages: search, list and detail view.

When disaggregated by role, agreement was consistent across stakeholders: Health Data Access Bodies (5.67/7) showed slightly higher support, followed by Data Users (5.33/7) and Data Holders (5.29/7). The relatively narrow range across roles suggests convergence on the importance of structured and visual presentation of F4P information.

Figure 25. Level of agreement of the F4P graphical user interfaces design feature.

The proposal to integrate filtering by purpose, F4P score thresholds, and the number of times used at the search level was generally supported, as was the idea of displaying purpose tags, scores, and usage metrics in listing views. At the dataset detail level, more advanced visualisation elements, such as sunburst diagrams for purposes and data quality dimensions, were generally well received.

However, qualitative feedback introduced an important nuance. One Data User emphasised that visual attractiveness and graphical representations should remain secondary to the

effectiveness and usability of search and filtering functions. In other words, F4P visualisation should enhance discoverability without compromising the rapid identification and comparison of datasets.

A further comment highlighted that, in some cases, the framing of voting questions was perceived as unclear, particularly when multiple design options were embedded within a single 1–7 agreement scale. This suggests that future consultations may benefit from more apparent separation between conceptual agreement and design alternatives.

Overall, the results indicate strong support for embedding F4P information directly into the HealthData@EU user journey, from search to detailed inspection. At the same time, implementation should prioritise functional usability and harmonised design, ensuring that visual sophistication does not overshadow clarity and comparability.

6.10. How - Use of RDF as underlying interoperability and computer readability component

A total of 9 participants voted in favour of using RDF as the underlying interoperability and machine-readable component for F4P data. The overall level of agreement was 5.67/7, indicating strong support for structuring F4P information in a semantically interoperable format.

Responses were concentrated in the upper range (5–7), with no strong disagreement recorded. This suggests that stakeholders broadly recognise the added value of a structured, linked-data approach for integrating F4P with datasets and the QUANTUM DQ&U&M label.

When disaggregated by role, Data Holders showed firm support (6.0/7), while Health Data Access Bodies expressed solid but slightly more moderate agreement (5.0/7). The difference is not substantial, but it may reflect greater operational caution on the part of HDABs regarding implementation complexity.

Figure 26. Level of agreement of the Use of RDF as underlying interoperability and computer readability component design feature.

The proposal to assign each dataset a dedicated RDF file containing all F4P data, linked via dataset UIDs and structured around the `dqv:UserQualityFeedback` model, was therefore generally well received. The possibility of aligning this structure with a future Health DCAT-AP extension was not explicitly contested.

However, qualitative feedback introduced several important considerations.

First, one Data Holder noted that the effectiveness of any technical model – including RDF – depends heavily on how the F4P score is defined and interpreted across datasets. In other words, semantic interoperability does not automatically ensure semantic comparability. If scoring methodologies are not harmonised, structured representation alone will not prevent inconsistent interpretation.

Second, concerns were raised about the practical adoption of semantic web technologies. One participant highlighted that RDF and related standards are not widely understood across all actors. This suggests that while the conceptual architecture is supported, capacity-building and technical guidance may be necessary to ensure consistent implementation.

Third, a broader concern was expressed regarding the implicit assumption of comparability across different types of datasets. Structured scoring, especially when exposed in interoperable formats, may create the impression that identical numerical values have equivalent meaning across domains. Participants stressed that this is not always the case and that contextual interpretation remains essential.

Overall, the results indicate clear support for using RDF as the technical backbone for F4P interoperability. At the same time, stakeholders emphasised that the success of this approach will depend less on the technology itself and more on methodological harmonisation, semantic clarity, and support for practical implementation.

7. Final recommendations

During the development of QUANTUM, the Fitness-for-purpose component has emerged as a key Data Quality indicator within the EHDS that complements the Fitness-for-use assessment captured in the QUANTUM label. While the QUANTUM label is self-reported by Data Holders following the QUANTUM specifications, the F4P is intended to be provided by Data Users, thus enabling a holistic view of Data Quality across all actors involved in data creation, access and secondary use. Health Data Access Bodies act as mediators and safeguards to ensure consistency and trustworthiness across the system.

The proposed initial design for F4P focuses on the structural and operational aspects needed to establish a functional system within the EHDS while remaining adaptable to future refinements in evaluation criteria. The definition of a specific F4P scoring methodology remains out of scope, although the proposed approach enables straightforward integration with QUANTUM Data Quality dimensions. Similarly, any future elaboration of F4P should be driven through a community-based, data-type-agnostic process, in line with the approach used for the QUANTUM Quality, Utility and Maturity label.

Table 1 presents the recommended design features for the F4P system.

Table 1 recommended design features for the F4P system

ID	Topic	Description
R.0	Initial assumption	F4P feedback is provided by the Data User for a dataset whose access was granted by the HDAB and the Data Holder. This feedback refers exclusively to the actual use of the dataset covered by the data permit.
R.1	Purposes and categories / classification / metadata	<p>F4P evaluations are tied to the purposes selected in the data access application. Users may optionally provide different evaluations if multiple purposes were selected.</p> <p>The main recommended purposes correspond to those listed in EHDS Article 53.1. However, additional more granular purposes should be added which could be optionally selected by Data Users.</p>
R.2	Scoring system	<p>For each dataset, the system provides:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An overall average F4P score across all evaluations. • Purpose-specific average scores based on the purposes defined in R.1. <p>The number of completed data uses is shown as a separate metric. Prospective users may also visualise trends of all scores and metrics over time.</p>
R.3	Assessment contents	<p>F4P assessments use the Data Quality dimensions defined in QUANTUM. Specific metrics will require further refinement.</p> <p>Each assessment may include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One free-text comment (with sufficient space for detail) <p>Optional supplemental material (user-generated DQ reports, analysis outputs, preprints, etc.), ideally as indexed digital objects (e.g., Zenodo, medRxiv).</p>
R.4	Availability of evaluations	Through HDAB catalogues, Data Users will have access to general and purpose-specific F4P scores, as well as the detailed evaluations from other users.
R.5	Moment of reporting	F4P feedback is submitted only after data use is completed, as indicated by the Data User, and must respect the deadlines in EHDS Article 61(4).

		Multiple sessions may be used to complete the feedback within the allowed timeframe.
R.6	Early feedback	Early feedback may be shared with Data Holders.
R.7	Validation	<p>Each feedback item is validated by the HDAB within a predefined timeframe.</p> <p>Validation includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Moderation of free text and supplemental materials ● A mechanism for DHs to review, agree/disagree, and respond to comments <p>DH responses are also validated by the HDAB. Feedback becomes public only after final HDAB validation.</p>
R.8	Technical means	A dedicated, EU-level open-source tool should support F4P reporting. It must interoperate with EHDS and HDAB systems and be reusable and extensible by HDABs.
R.9	User interfaces at HealthData@EU	<p>F4P information could appear in three stages (see Figure 27):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Searching datasets: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Filters for purposes, score thresholds, and number of uses. ● Search results list: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Display purpose tags, associated scores, and usage counts. ● Dataset detail page: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ General: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Sunburst diagram (or similar), showing purpose-level scores. ■ List of all F4P feedback (sortable), including scores, comments, and supplemental materials. ○ For each purpose: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Sunburst chart showing DQ-dimension-specific scores.
R.10	RDF representation	<p>Each dataset will have an RDF file containing all F4P data (Figure 28), linked to the dataset UID and the QUANTUM DQ&U&M label, with 1:1 cardinality for the overall F4P score and N:1 cardinality for the individual feedback.</p> <p>The root class is dqv:UserQualityFeedback (a subclass of dqv:QualityAnnotation), targeting the evaluated dataset (oa:hasTarget). Multiple entries under oa:hasBody represent the multidimensional review (text, per-dimension ratings, etc.).</p>
R.11	Other considerations	<p>The F4P system must follow user-centred design principles.</p> <p>Data Holders may include in the dataset information warnings about potential misuses for certain purposes to avoid unnecessary requests.</p>

Figure 27. Potential visual mock-ups for the F4P component in the HealthData@EU platform. Left: Dataset search and listing interface, where purposes can be used as filters and F4P scores are displayed in the results. Center: Overall F4P scores by purpose, shown in a sunburst-style diagram. The QUANTUM DQ&U&M label (top, dotted square) is displayed for reference. A second set of sunburst diagrams (bottom) illustrates purpose-specific F4P scores using the QUANTUM Data Quality dimensions. Right: List of all individual F4P assessments submitted by Data Users, including scores, free-text comments, and any supplemental material.

Figure 28. Example of a possible RDF representation for the Fitness-for-purpose evaluation (right) linked with the contents on the QUANTUM DQ&U&M Label (left), both targeting the dataset distribution (using the dcat:Distribution class). The F4P information can use the dqv:UserQualityFeedback class, whose body and contents may further use specific classes and properties to represent the required components.

A major topic of debate was whether F4P reporting should be mandatory. On that design feature, both in the Workshop and in the Project Forum, responses showed a high level of disagreement. Despite Article 61(4) requiring Data Users to provide information on data use, its obligatoriness related to the F4P feedback remains a challenge. Incentives may play a key role, always balancing potential discrimination issues (e.g., prioritised access). A frequent comment was that obligatoriness may lead to low quality reports, or even a barrier discouraging data usage by extra burden.

The former belongs to a set of remaining discussion points that arose in light of no or few agreement during the three phases of this work, as detailed in the previous sections. Table 2 summarizes these discussion points.

Table 2 F4P discussion points linked to recommendations

ID	Topic	Description	Linked to Recommendation ID
D0	Obligatoriness	Whether F4P should be mandatory; potential incentives; risks.	R.0
D1.1	Purposes and categories	Inclusion of more fine-grained purposes (faceted lists, keywords, vocabularies).	R.1

D1.2		Allow DUs to specify health domain or study target to complement metadata.	R.1
D1.3		Handling cases where multiple datasets are used for the same purpose under one permit.	R.1
D2.1	Scoring system	More granular purposes may also have specific F4P scores.	R.2
D2.2		Concerns about averaging purposes due to potential bias/misinterpretation.	R.2
D3	Assessment contents	Tooling for HDABs to verify DH-provided QUANTUM labels against DU feedback.	R.3
D4	Availability of evaluations	Show only DU institution, never individual details. Potential to add the type/category of Data User / respondent to allow filtering.	R.4
D5	Validation	Resource needs for moderation at HDABs.	R.7
D6.1	F4P reporting	F4P feedback should exclude issues related to the Data Access Application.	R.0
D6.2		How to handle withdrawn applications (e.g., insufficient data).	R.0
D6.3		Resource planning for maintaining the F4P tool.	R.8
D7	Early feedback	Whether early feedback should be internal DU-DH messaging or public Questions & Answers.	R.6
D8	RDF	Potential evolution to a Health DCAT-AP extension.	R.10

The recommendations presented in this report position the F4P component as a strategic component to the EHDS. By incorporating Data User feedback, the HealthData@EU secondary use framework can evolve dynamically, complement and reinforce the reliability of the QUANTUM label, and enable continuous improvement among Data Holders. Addressing the remaining open questions—particularly about obligatoriness, validation, and purpose granularity—will be essential for ensuring the F4P system is both effective and widely adopted. With continued refinement, the F4P system can be a key component for a trustworthy, user-centred, and evidence-driven HealthData@EU ecosystem.

8. References

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- [4] TEHDAS 2 Deliverable 6.3 - [TEHDAS - WP6 - D6.3 - Recommendations on a Data Quality Framework for the European Health Data Space for secondary use](#)
- [5] QUANTUM labelling tool - [QUANTUM - The Health Data Quality Label](#)